

European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving
the Energy Transition

D6.5 - Repository of best practices and solutions for ET

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofunded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to develop and implement a methodology to enhance and facilitate multi-level governance for energy transition in public authorities and the coordinated adoption of Energy Transition Measures for achieving the European sustainability targets.

The objective of Deliverable 6.5 is to collect information from the ePLANET partners and their networks to develop a Repository of best practices and solutions for Energy Transition, produced in the framework of Task 6.3 "Best practices and solutions for energy transition." The ePLANET partner coordinating the Task is the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES), and contributions are foreseen in particular from partners CIMNE and LIMA, as well as from the rest of the partners and their networks.

The concept for the Repository of best practices and solutions for Energy Transition is to be a 'one-stop-shop' for any public authority and other interested stakeholders, to source best practices and respective case studies, in the following four key aspects related to energy transition:

- Governance practices & structures
- Technical solutions
- Funding mechanisms
- Training - capacity building"

The Repository is developed by consolidating information to be collected using a specific Excel template (part of deliverable 6.5). It is in report format and will be modified into a searchable database on the ePLANET project website.

The Repository will be available online after the end of the project, as a useful tool for supporting the long-term sustainability of the project and capitalisation of the project outcomes.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CCR	Carbon Climate Registry
CDP	Carbon Disclosure Project (non-profit charity that runs the global disclosure system to manage environmental impacts)
CEMR	Council of European Municipalities and Regions
CETA	Clean Energy Transition Agenda
CIMNE	International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering
CRES	Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
DDGI	Girona Provincial Council
DSO	Distributor System Operator (Utility Company)
DL	Decree Law
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ET	Energy Transition
GCoM	Global Covenant of Mayors
ICAEN	Catalan Institute for Energy
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ISEAP	Island Sustainable Energy Plan
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan(s)
NSRF	National Strategic Reference Framework
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Buildings
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
PA	Public Authority(ies)
RAP	Regional Action Plan
RD	Royal Decree
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
RDL	Royal Decree Law
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SAC	Strategic Advisory Committee
SE(C)AP	Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plan
SMAP	Sustainable Mobility Action Plan

1 Introduction

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofunded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims to deploy new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET aims at deploying Energy Transition (ET) in the public sector. The main challenges are:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments,
- Enhancing the decision-making process in the deployment of ET projects,
- Providing coherence and consistency to the energy transition measures (ETM) to be implemented,
- Encouraging the digitalisation of measures and plans,
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools.

These targeted objectives will support the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

2 Data collection

The following sections provide short profiles of the project partners that provided requested data to an excel sheet to CRES and were the baseline for the preparation of this report:

PP03 - Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES)

CRES is based in Athens, in the Region of Attica (Greece). It is the Greek national centre for Renewable Energy Sources (RES), Rational Use of Energy (RUE) and Energy Saving (ES). It is also appointed by Law as the National Coordinating Centre in Greece for supporting the implementation of national policy for improving energy efficiency, including energy-efficiency in buildings, and the promotion of RES. It offers technical support to the Ministry of Environment and Energy as well as to public entities at regional and local level, for developing and implementing energy renovation plans and projects for public buildings. CRES is also the National coordinator of the Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, providing technical support to local authorities for developing and implementing their sustainable energy action plans.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordination of Tasks 2.2, 3.5; Coordination of WP6; Technical support to the RDFC for WP3 pilot activities; Transferring activities at national level.

PP01 - International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE)

CIMNE is based in Barcelona, in the Region of Catalonia (Spain). It is a leading research and technological development institution with a proven ability to deliver big data management services in energy, building and environment fields.

In ePLANET, CIMNE is the project coordinator, technology provider and responsible for the ePLANET platform development. The EU project ePLANET is a logical progress of CIMNE BEE Group's dedicated department, providing innovative solutions for local public authorities to drive them in the Energy Transition.

Its main roles in the project include: Project coordinator; Responsible of WP1, WP3; Coordination of Tasks 2.3, 2.5.

PP02 - Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN)

ICAEN is based in Barcelona, in the Region of Catalonia (Spain). It is the entity of the Government of Catalonia responsible for developing and carrying out the Catalan energy policy, especially in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energies. ICAEN develops programs to promote RES and energy efficiency in all economic sectors: industry, transport, primary and buildings. ICAEN is in charge of buildings Energy Performance Certification in Catalonia and leads the Energy Efficiency Plan of the Catalan Government buildings. In addition, ICAEN is involved and works jointly with the local community in the development of energy efficiency actions in municipal buildings, public lighting and efficient mobility. Likewise, ICAEN collaborates with other Ministries of the Catalan Government to develop transversal actions such as the National Agreement for the Energy Transition of Catalonia, the Action Plan for Energy Efficiency in Industry, the Catalan Strategy for Energy Renovation of Buildings or the Biomass Strategy.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordinator of WP2 (Governance); support to the rest of the tasks; Participation in Capacity building and training in Municipalities of Catalonia; Dissemination at a local level of project outputs.

PP04 - European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and Environment (FEDARENE)

FEDARENE is based in Brussels (Belgium). FEDARENE is the premier European network of regional and local organisations which implement, co-ordinate and facilitate energy and environment policies. Regional and local agencies, regional governments and departments working in these fields, are represented in FEDARENE.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: EU wide replication; Organisation of stakeholder engagement activities; Coordination of WP5.

PP05 - ICLEI Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI EURO)

ICLEI is based in Freiburg im Breisgau, in Germany. It is a global network working with more than 2,500 local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development. Active in 125+ countries, ICLEI influences sustainability policy and drives local action for low emission, nature-based, equitable, resilient and circular development. Its Members and team of experts work together through peer exchange, partnerships and capacity building to create systemic change for urban sustainability.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Supporting continuous engagement, feedback and project EU-wide replication; Leading Task 6.2 and responsible for D6.3 and D6.4; Contributing to all WPs.

PP06 - Girona Provincial Council (DDGI)

Diputació de Girona (Girona Provincial Council) is based in Girona, in the Region of Catalonia (Spain). It is the public local authority for the Girona province and provides technical, financial and administrative support to all the 221 Municipalities within its operational area. It is a Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy Coordinator and one of their main stakeholders in the province of Girona. It supports all municipalities to sign, join and develop their own Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plan.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordination of the pilot application in the pilot region of Girona province; Contribution to all Work Packages, with a special focus on the multi-level regional governance (WP2) and the scaling-up to the whole region and replication activities (WP6).

PP07 - Regional Development Fund of Crete (RDFC)

RDFC is based in the city of Heraklion, in the Region of Crete (Greece). It is a public entity under private law, established in February 1998 and it was assumed an important role in the implementation of an innovative institution, aimed at supporting Regional Development of the elected (2011) Regional authorities and the process of decentralization in Greece. Under the RDFC, operates the Regional Energy Agency of Crete (REAC), established in 1994 by the Region of Crete and the European Commission as one of the first Energy Regional Agencies in Europe and the first at regional level in Greece.

REAC is the Regional Coordinator-for the whole island of Crete-of the EU Covenant of Mayors initiative and a member of the Covenant of Islands.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordination of the pilot application in the pilot region of Crete; Contribution to the multi-level regional governance (WP2) as the regional coordinator of the CoM and to all other WPs of the project.

PP08 - Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK)

EAZK is based in the City of Zlín, in the Zlín Region (Czech Republic). It is a non-profit organisation. It is a regional energy agency established in 2006 and 100% owned by the Zlín Region. EAZK was primarily established as an implementing tool of the Zlín Region energy policy.

EAZK operates within the whole area of the Zlín Region which is identical with NUTS 3-CZ072 . The EAZK is a project partner with a great potential to address various target groups as the agency provides energy management for more than 150 organisations established both by the Zlín Region and particular municipalities.

Since 2014 EAZK has been Covenant of Mayors Supporter and takes action on territories of the Zlín Region in the field of energy to promote the Covenant of Mayors initiative and support municipalities in their effort to adapt their local level policy and goals to be in synergies with existing Covenant of Mayors goals.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Representative of the Pilot Region (Zlín Region), coordinating the pilot implementation; Contribution to the Work Packages, with particular focus on the transferring activities (scaling up to the whole region, replication to other regions) but also on capacity building (user's empowerment, WP4), the definition and deployment of clustering groups and governance methodology, and the institutionalization of ePLANET outcomes.

3 Practices and Solutions in Governance

This chapter records successful governance practices and structures. Best practice solutions for effective multi-level governance coordination between regional and local energy action plans, such as digitalising plans and setting up permanent governance structures, are included. Case studies of public authorities that demonstrate novel/effective implementation of multi-level governance are also included.

Table 3-1. Committee with participation of Region and its Municipalities, to coordinate energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Committee with participation of Region and its Municipalities, to coordinate energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings
Keywords:	Public authorities' cooperation
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Multi-level governance
	Governance structure
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Spain, Greece, Spain, Italy, Malta, Croatia
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Catalonia-Spain, Crete-Greece, Valencia-Spain, Emilia-Romagna-Italy, Lazio-Italy, Abruzzo-Italy, Gozo-Malta, Dubrovnik-Neretva- Croatia
Short description:	Multi-level governance in Regions and Municipalities, for coordinating energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	During the implementation of SHERPA, there was a proposal for setting up a formal governance structure to coordinate energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings, coordinated by each SHERPA participating Region, with the participation of all respective Municipalities in the territory of the Region. In the Region of Crete (partner of SHERPA), the proposal was for such a Committee that would be coordinated by the Region, with the participation of energy managers of Regional buildings, designated personnel from the Region technical, development & financial departments, and participation of designated representatives from all 24 Municipalities of Crete (e.g. CoM contact person in each Municipality, energy managers of Municipal buildings etc.)
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	Eventually this governance structure was not set up as a formal deliverable of SHERPA, so in the case of the Region of Crete, it was not formally set up and does not currently operate, however it could be further explored in future.
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.]	
Project full title / acronym:	SHARED knowledge for Energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations / SHERPA
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	Interreg MED 2014-2020
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	11/2016
End date:	10/2019
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	By adopting the SHERPA methodology, 8 Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps were developed, for the participating Mediterranean partner Regions (Catalonia-Spain, Crete-Greece, Valencia-Spain, Emilia-Romagna-Italy, Lazio-Italy, Abruzzo-Italy, Gozo-Malta, Dubrovnik-Neretva- Croatia).
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEYmSTW0-ozsEgww_6R2cHQ
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://www.facebook.com/SHERPAMED

Table 3-2. Identification of energy governance actors in Catalonia and Greece.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Identification of energy governance actors in Catalonia and Greece.
Keywords:	Governance structure Energy Efficiency in buildings Methodology / tool / solution
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Identification of energy governance actors in Catalonia and Greece (energy managers; policy makers; public authorities; EPC-based management).
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	BIGG aims at demonstrating the application of big data technologies and data analytic techniques for the complete buildings life-cycle of more than 4,000 buildings in Catalonia and Greece. Catalan pilot site main actors identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~ 100 energy managers, responsible for the management of public buildings, having a weekly or monthly interaction with the energy management tool ~ 20-30 policy makers responsible for planning actions to improve energy performance of buildings with a monthly or bi-annual interaction with the tool ~ 10 public authorities on special interest on general building trends, having semi-annual or annual interaction with the tool. Greek pilot site two business cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 17 large commercial office buildings in Athens managed through Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) and Maintenance Contract. Delivering flexibility services by managing appliances of residential and commercial consumers of electricity and natural gas, spread across various cities of Greece.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Building Information aGGregation, harmonization and analytics platform / BIGG
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Horizon 2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://www.bigg-project.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	1/12/2020
End date: If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	30/11/2023
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	BIGG is a 36-month project launched in December 2020. It demonstrates the application of big data technologies and data analytic techniques in the complete building life-cycle in more than 4000 buildings in 6 large-scale pilots, 3 in Spain (Catalonia) and 3 in Greece. As part of BIGG architecture, the project has developed an open, cloud-based, building-related data analytics toolbox that supports different data analysis techniques and is extensible to support third-party developments and a wide range of services.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	BIGG Web url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/ Catalan pilot url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/bigg-project-pilots-business-cases-and-use-cases/ Greek pilot url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/bigg-project-pilots-business-cases-and-use-cases-in-greece/

Table 3-3. One-stop-shop digital platform to allow better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	One-stop-shop digital platform to allow better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Pilot sites in Spain and Bulgaria.
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	One-stop-shop digital platform to allow better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	EN-TRACK aims to enable a one-stop-shop platform to allow a better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings. The platform will allow to make better decisions for de-risking investments in energy efficiency projects for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial institutions • Building owners
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings / EN-TRACK
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Horizon 2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://en-track.eu/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	01/11/2020
End date:	31/10/2023
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://en-track.eu/

Table 3-4. Establishment of EU Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG), as a structure for accelerating private finance to energy efficiency.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Establishment of EU Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG), as a structure for accelerating private finance to energy efficiency.
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Governance structure
	Innovative financing
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Establishment of EU Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG), as a structure for accelerating private finance to energy efficiency.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.]	The Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG) established in 2013 by the European Commission Directorate-General for Energy and the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI). EEFIG work is providing a significant contribution in accelerating private finance to energy efficiency.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform / DEEP-EEFIG
Funding Programme: (if applicable)	European Commission's Directorate-General for Energy
Project website: (if applicable)	https://deep.ec.europa.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date: If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	EEFIG addresses barriers to energy efficiency financing through both policy design and market-based solutions to increase the scale of energy efficiency investments across Europe. Composed of over 300 representatives from more than 200 organisations, EEFIG's strength are its members - spanning public and private financial institutions, industry representatives and sector experts. EEFIG works through working groups that target specific themes. Through a multi-level stakeholder dialogue, working groups identify opportunities and barriers in the long-term financing for energy efficiency, and propose policy and market solutions.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	<p>EEFIG web url-EN: https://ec.europa.eu/eefig/index_en</p> <p>DEEP web url-EN: https://ec.europa.eu/eefig/going-activities_en</p> <p>DEEP platform url-EN: https://deep.ec.europa.eu/</p>

Table 3-5. Coordinated project of biomass implementation in 22 Municipalities in Girona.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Coordinated project of biomass implementation in 22 Municipalities in Girona.
Keywords:	Public authorities' cooperation
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy transition measures
	Renewable energy
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Province of Girona
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description:	Biomass implementation in 22 Municipalities in Girona: installation of 7 biomass boilers, 15 biomass heat networks and 2 forest biomass facilities.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	Local Authorities/Municipalities: 22 municipalities were involved in the project. 7 biomass boilers were installed, 15 biomass heat networks were constructed and 2 forest biomass treatment facilities were built. The project had a total cost of 3,982,391.24 euros, 50% of which was financed by ERDF funds, 24% by the Girona Provincial Council, and 26% by the Municipalities involved.
Project full title / acronym:	
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Boilers, heat networks and facilities for chip production / Bebiomassgi
Funding Programme:	ERDF
(If applicable)	
Project website:	https://www.ddgi.cat/web/servei/3372/calderes--xarxes-de-calor-i-instal·lacions-per-a-la-produccio-d-estella-operacio-go03-000003
(If applicable)	
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	The project has launched a new project called ForesHEAT, which provides online monitoring of forest biomass consumption. A free service to monitor and manage biomass installations for municipalities, biomass suppliers or energy service companies.
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	Video results url-CAT: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lzf3V9YkFNA
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	ForesHEAT url-CAT: https://www.forestheat.cat/

Table 3-6. Adoption of EPC Facilitator role to foster EPC contracts.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Adoption of EPC Facilitator role to foster EPC contracts.
Keywords:	Governance structure
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Innovative financing
	Energy transition measures
	Training seminars
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	The project introduced the new figure of "EPC facilitator" to foster energy equipment renovation using EPC contracting.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	The project introduced a new figure, "EPC facilitator" as a key driver to foster EPC contracts. Main function: to give guidance and advising in those installations willing to do energy equipment renovation, to be done using the EPC contracting. Trainings conducted for the new EPC facilitators.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	
Project full title / acronym:	Energy efficiency with Performance guarantees in the private and public sector / guarantEE
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	Horizon 2020
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://guarantee-project.eu/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	1/4/2016
End date:	31/3/2019
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	GuarantEE Precheck EPC tool: http://www.epccheck.eu/
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	

Table 3-7. Guidance and advice by the Girona Provincial Council to local councils wishing to promote local energy communities.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Guidance and advice by the Girona Provincial Council to local councils wishing to promote local energy communities.
Keywords:	Governance structure
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy communities
	Renewable energy
	Public authorities' cooperation
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Province of Girona
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Girona Provincial Council offers technical and financial support to local councils that wish to promote local energy communities and install PVs.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance: etc.]	Girona Provincial Council is promoting this pioneering project in Spain, offering technical and financial support to local councils that wish to promote local energy communities. Photovoltaic solar panels are installed on municipal facilities, supplying electricity to the buildings themselves, to homes in energy poverty and to all those who wish to join the community
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Comunitats Locals d'Energia / Local Energy Communities
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Girona Provincial Council's Service Plan and Action Plan
Project website: (If applicable)	-
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	90 projects of energy local communities already done or started a project. Progress in 2022: 46 municipalities have initiated the drafting of these reports for the implementation of local energy communities and 27 more will start soon.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	Guide url-CAT New guide launch url-CAT New project launch url-CAT

Table 3-8. Innovative Public-Private-Citizen-Partnership (PPCP) for energy governance at local level.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Innovative Public-Private-Citizen-Partnership (PPCP) for energy governance at local level.
Keywords:	Governance structure
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy transition measures
	Multi-level governance
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	City of Viladecans, Catalonia.
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	VILAWATT project tried to create an innovative Public-Private-Citizen organizational structure for energy governance at local level in Catalonia.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	VILAWATT project tried to create an innovative Public-Private-Citizen organizational structure (PPCP), for energy governance at local level (in the city of Viladecans, Catalonia).
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Innovative local public-private-citizen partnership for energy governance / Vilawatt
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	UIA (2016 – 2019)
Project website: (If applicable)	https://uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/viladecans
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	11/01/2016
End date:	31/10/2019
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	A mindset change in the local population, through enhanced knowledge and capacities related to energy transition and renovation of buildings. A new PPCP organization for energy governance that will empower and engage citizens, local administration and public sector for the energy transition. A deep renovation of 60 dwellings, supported by a participative scheme, and given high visibility.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	https://uia-initiative.eu/sites/default/files/2016-12/Viladecans%20-%20MEDIA%20-%20PPT%20presentation.pdf

Table 3-9. Achieving multi-level governance in energy and climate planning.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Achieving multi-level governance in energy and climate planning.
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
	Public authorities' cooperation
	Energy transition measures
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	Austria, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, Romania.
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	C-Track 50 main goal was to achieve multi-level governance in energy and climate planning.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	C-Track 50 focused on the multi-level governance models adopted in 11 countries and drew conclusions and recommendations on implementing and tailoring collaboration processes. Achieving multi-level governance in energy and climate planning was one of the main goals of C-Track50. The project linked up EU, national, regional and local authorities to establish multi-level cooperation and ensure synergies when developing and implementing sustainable energy and climate policy plans. This collaboration facilitated integrated planning and linked up national energy and climate priorities and efforts with regional and local policies and actions. Additionally, capacity building activities covered knowledge gaps and needs at a regional and local level, so that local and regional authorities are empowered to develop integrated energy and climate policy plans for 2050, but also to secure funding for the implementation of selected actions.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	C-TRACK 50
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Horizon 2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://www.c-track50.eu
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	C-Track 50 employed an innovative approach in empowering regional/local authorities, by building their capacity and addressing barriers in energy planning, as well as enabling them to actively contribute to the EU's long term energy policy targets, by introducing the carbon neutrality concept at regional/local level, ensuring at the same time multi governance collaboration at all levels to facilitate the planning process. In conclusion, C-Track 50 applied this innovative approach and engaged national and sub-national authorities in eleven (11) countries, and as a result it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitated the development and implementation of one hundred and seven (107) integrated sustainable energy and climate resilient plans at a local level, Provided recommendations/facilitated the development of eleven (11) integrated sustainable energy and climate resilient plans at a regional level and, Provided recommendations for establishing new/revising existing energy and climate policies at a national level, in line with the carbon neutrality target by 2050.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	Existing Multi-level Governance Models in 11 EU Countries: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/Briefing_paper_final.pdf Putting Regions on Track for Carbon Neutrality by 2050 - Final Publishable Report - November 2021 https://c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/2021/Final%20Publishable%20Report%20%282%29.pdf Energy Planning Process Report in 11 EU Countries: https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/View%20Report.pdf Guidebook for achieving Carbon Neutrality by 2050 https://c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/2021-06/Guidebook_for_Achieving_Carbon_Neutrality_by_2050.pdf Recommendations on national energy priorities in the eleven participating countries https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/C-Track50_DeI_D2_5.pdf C-Track 50 Knowledge Repository: https://www.c-track50.eu/knowledge-repository

Table 3-10. Establishment of Regional observatories for energy transition at local level.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Establishment of Regional observatories for energy transition at local level.
Keywords:	Governance structure
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Multi-level governance
	Energy transition planning
	Public authorities' cooperation
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Data4Action introduced regional observatories as a structure for implementing energy transition strategies and planning at local level.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	Data4Action introduced regional observatories. These regional observatories are powerful tools for implementing efficient strategies at the local level. Most of the structures are governed by a local consortium gathering at least several public authorities and energy data suppliers. They are very often supported by public authorities and integrated within existing regional organizations such as energy agencies or public departments. The added value of this kind of structure is its high level of technical skills in data gathering and analysis, and in energy planning.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	DATA4ACTION
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Intelligent Energy Europe
Project website: (If applicable)	https://fedarene.org/project/data4action/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	Within the Data4Action project, 4 Regional Energy Observatories: Oreges Rhône Alpes (FR), Energieluppen of Norrbotten (SE), Ligurian Energy and Environment Observatory (IT) & Climate Observatory Nord-Pas de Calais (FR) have supported the creation of 7 new ones in Alba (RO), Carlow Kilkenny (IE), Torino (IT), Plovdiv (BG), Zlín (CZ), Kent (UK) and Greece.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	Data4Action – Energy data sharing for sustainable energy planning: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D4A_final-publishable-report.pdf Data4Action – Policy recommendations on improving energy data sharing for effective energy planning at sub-national levels: https://fedarene.org/publication/policy-recommendations-on-improving-energy-data-sharing-for-effective-energy-planning-at-sub-national-levels/ Data4Action – Data Access Guidebook for SEAPs: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/valide-16-04-2017D4A-6.2_Leaflet_EU.pdf Data4Action – Project Leaflet: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/valide-16-04-2017D4A-6.2_Leaflet_EU.pdf

Table 3-11. Establishment of Permanent Cluster of national HUBs in the Blue Energy sector.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Establishment of Permanent Cluster of national HUBs in the Blue Energy sector.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Governance structure Multi-level governance Energy transition planning Renewable energy
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Multiple countries
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	PELAGOS aims to establish a permanent Cluster of national HUBs in the Blue Energy sector in the Mediterranean.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	PELAGOS aims to establish a permanent Cluster of national HUBs in the Blue Energy (BE) sector, where technical experiences are shared. Permanent communication among actors is a crucial asset for the evolution and advancement of the project and its effective contribution to the Blue Growth of Mediterranean coastal, insular and offshore regions. The specific scope of PELAGOS is to facilitate the deployment of targeted technological solutions and products that are tailored to the characteristics of the Mediterranean environment
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	PELAGOS
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://pelagos.interreg-med.eu/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	2019
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i>	Blue Energy Cluster Building Methodology Diagnostic study of the Mediterranean marine energy resources potential Existing Policy and regulatory status on MED Blue Energy development Deployment potential assessment of Blue Energy Technologies for MED key Maritime industries

Table 3-12. Web platform for public consultation with local community, on Municipal strategy for climate neutrality in Heraklion (Crete).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Web platform for public consultation with local community, on Municipal strategy for climate neutrality in Heraklion (Crete).
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
	Methodology / tool / solution
Country:	Greece
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	Municipality of Heraklion, Crete
Short description:	Preparation by the Municipality of Heraklion of web-platform for public consultation with local community on energy transition planning.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	Participation in this EU Mission for climate neutral and smart cities by 2030 will ensure that these cities act as experimentation and innovation hubs to put all European cities in a position to become climate-neutral by 2050.
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	With its participation, the Municipality of Heraklion prepared a web-platform for public consultation on the different measures identified within the Municipal Strategy for climate neutrality and aspires to meet the challenges arising from the transition by organizing with reliability, transparency and inclusiveness a process of continuous and effective consultation with the local community. At least 2.000 residences will be influenced by the Municipality's annual initiative of conducting energy inspections and consultations (the so-called "participative energy transition" initiative) to proceed to at least minor (e.g. behavioural) actions. The purpose of the action is to achieve citizens behavioural shift towards rational use of energy in their houses.
Project full title / acronym:	
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Heraklion 2030 "Climate-Neutral & Smart City"
Funding Programme:	Horizon Europe (2021-2027)
(If applicable)	
Project website:	https://mission100.heraklion.gr/
(If applicable)	
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Heraklion Municipality was not included in the 10 EU cities selected in April 2022 but in light of the overwhelming interest from 377 cities to join the mission, the Commission is putting in place support for cities that were not selected, including support through the Mission Platform and funding opportunities under the Cities Mission Work Programme of Horizon Europe.
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_2591
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	https://www.intelligentcitieschallenge.eu/cities/heraklion

Table 3-13. Open call to Municipalities to upgrade their water systems with the installation of telemetry, automation and leak control systems, under the National Operational Program.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Open call to Municipalities to upgrade their water systems with the installation of telemetry, automation and leak control systems, under the National Operational Program.
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition measures
	Methodology / tool / solution
Country:	Greece
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Region of Crete
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description:	Open call to Municipalities to upgrade their water systems with the installation of telemetry, automation and leak control systems, under the National Operational Program.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	An open call to all Municipalities and their Municipal sewage services was released in 2017 and six (6) Municipalities of Crete (Rethymno, Maleviziou, Chania, Hersonissos, Minoa Pediadas, Agios Nikolaos) were successfully evaluated in 2018 to upgrade their water systems with the installation of telemetry, automation and leak control systems. The data will be managed remotely from the existing and new Local Water Control Stations for the overall management of the water distribution in each Municipality.
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	
Project full title / acronym:	Telemetry & remote-control of leaks in new water networks, expanding automation to new local stations and upgrading local automation control stations (SCADA).
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme:	Greece National Operational program for Transport Infrastructure, Environment and Sustainable Development) of the NSRF 2014-2020
(If applicable)	
Project website:	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/EN/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/greece/2014gr16m1op001
(If applicable)	
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Rational management of water resources and improvement of the quality of water stock while reducing leaks.
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	https://government.gov.gr/88-6-ekat-evro-stous-ota-gia-tin-anavathmisi-ton-diktion-idrefsis-ke-ton-periorismo-ton-diarron/
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	

Table 3-14. Evaluation of Cretan Municipalities under the framework of the National and Regional Operational Programmes, so as to undertake energy upgrade projects in public buildings.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Evaluation of Cretan Municipalities under the framework of the National and Regional Operational Programmes, so as to undertake energy upgrade projects in public buildings
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy transition planning
	Energy transition measures
Country:	Greece
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Region of Crete
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description:	Evaluation of Cretan Municipalities under the National and Regional Operational Programmes, for energy upgrade projects in public buildings.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	Many Cretan municipalities (i.e. Heraklion, Ierapetra) were successfully evaluated under the framework of the National Operational Programme in order to upgrade the energy efficiency of Sports Facilities (Pancretan Stadium in Heraklion and Gym named Markos Foniadakis in Ierapetra). Similarly, 15 new projects related to energy savings in public buildings were included in the Regional Operational Program "CRETE 2014-2020". These projects include energy upgrade of public buildings, in order to achieve the goals set in the National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency. They concern: the Indoor Gym of Tavronitis, the City Hall of Platanias and, in Rethymno, the building of the Regional Unit, the City Hall and the 1st High School of the city. Also, the Gymnasiums of Platanias and Souda, the Gymnasiums - Lyceums of Alikianos and Agia Varvara, the school complexes of Amberia and Koumbe of Chania, the 2nd Primary School of Archanes and the Gymnasium - EPAL of Kantanos.
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	
Project full title / acronym:	Actions of Energy Upgrading and Energy Saving (EE) and Utilization of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in Sports Facilities
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme:	Greek National Operational Program "Transport Infrastructure, Environment and Sustainable Development" and Regional Operational Program of Crete 2014-2020
(If applicable)	
Project website:	http://www.rethymno.gr
(If applicable)	
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	Annual implementation report: https://ymeperaa.gr/images/Implementation_report_2014GR16M1OP001_2020_0_el.pdf Indicative study for the sports centre in Chania Municipality: https://www.chania.gr/files/55/44814/06_tehniki_ekthesi_naytathlitikoy_soydas_signed.pdf?md=1637663502 Programme information
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available).	

Table 3-15. Involvement of secondary school pupils as "Energy Inspectors", in Municipality of Hersonisos (Crete).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Involvement of secondary school pupils as "Energy Inspectors", in Municipality of Hersonisos (Crete).
Keywords:	Governance structure
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Greece
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Crete
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Role of "Energy Inspector" played by pupils in their school building, studying and practicing on buildings' energy efficiency.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	Pupils played the role of the "Energy Inspector", by measuring the total surface of the walls and open spaces of their school building, the Town Hall and their library building. Energy consumption was calculated as well as carbon dioxide emissions, according to standards set out by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. During the project's implementation, pupils studied, with the aid of a voluntary Energy Inspector, the Greek legislative framework on energy and the recent rules on buildings' energy efficiency. The need for this project came up due to the information gap that pupils and young people in general, have on the irreversible effects of human activity on climate change.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Junior Energy Inspectors in Action in the Municipality of Hersonisos
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Implemented under the framework of the 1st Grade curriculum in Greek schools for the elaboration of a scientific project.
Project website: (If applicable)	http://www.hersonisos.gr
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	Pupils becoming aware of the effects of climate change and in particular the relation of energy consumption with increment of carbon dioxide emissions. In addition, studying ways of reducing energy consumption and introducing renewable energy resources.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	https://www.hersonisos.gr/en/municipal/schoollproject1/schoolproject.html https://kede.gr/chersonisos-oi-energeiakoi-epitheorites-junior-analamvanoun-kai-pali-drasi/

Table 3-16. Memorandum of Understanding among the Region of Crete and 13 Cretan municipalities, for the energy upgrading of public installations.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Memorandum of Understanding among the Region of Crete and 13 Cretan municipalities, for the energy upgrading of public installations.
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures
	Public lighting
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Country:	Greece
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Crete
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	MoU among Region of Crete and 13 Municipalities, for the energy upgrade of public installations (municipal lighting, hospitals and health centres).
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.]</i>	A Memorandum of Understanding was signed among the Region of Crete and 13 Cretan municipalities describing responsibilities of each involved stakeholder within the INTERACT in CRETE project in order to proceed in the energy upgrading of all relevant installations (municipal public lighting, hospitals and health centres). The interventions for the energy upgrade of public lighting are expected to have an overall reduction by 69% in energy consumption from the sector. The ultimate goal of ELENA project is the creation of energy communities for net metering, virtual net-metering and the installation of integrated photovoltaic panels.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	INTEgrated sustainable enERgy ACTions and projects in Crete / INTERACT in Crete
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	ELENA (European Local ENergy Assistance) - European Investment Bank ELENA provides technical assistance for energy efficiency and renewable energy investments targeting buildings and innovative urban transport.
Project website: (If applicable)	https://www.eib.org/attachments/documents/119-project-factsheet-interact-in-crete.pdf
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	The project officially started on 16/12/2020 with the signature of the contract between the Region of Crete and the European Investment Bank. In March 2022 the Region of Crete released a call for the public procurement of maturation studies for the Energy Upgrade - Automation of the Street Lighting System in the Urban Lighting System of 8 Municipalities of the Region of Crete (Archanon-Asterousion, Phaistou, Mylopotamou, Apokorona, Amariou, Heraklion, Hersonissos). In April 2022 the Region of Crete released a call for the public procurement of maturation studies for the Energy Upgrading of Hospitals, Health Centers and Other Public Buildings in the Region of Crete.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i>	https://www.eib.org/en/products/advising/elena/index.htm

Table 3-17. Multivel governance in the Zlín Region.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Multivel governance in the Zlín Region
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Governance structure
	EU funding
	Renewable energy
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Country:	Czech Republic
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Zlín Region
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region, established in 2006 on a basis of project submitted by the Zlín Region to the Intelligent Energy programme together with province of Mantova in Italy and city of Gijón in Asturias region in Spain. The main aim/target of the agency is successful promotion of utilization of renewable energy sources in various sectors and contribution to increasing of the energy efficiency on both regional and local levels and also play an active role in building partnership between private and public sector.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	The MLG and its further development for the Zlín Region are just the role and commitment of the Energy Agency of the Zlín region. The EAZK is 100% owned by the Zlín Region, it is the public organization and all the projects and activities carried out by the EAZK are funded, cofounded or pre financed by the Zlín Region.
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	There are not direct regional financial support mechanisms to support local authority investments in sustainable energy solutions in the Zlín Region, however, EAZK plays the role of the indirect financial support for that.
	EAZK as a CoM supporter provides in the Zlín Region activities related to coordinating structures of the CoM initiative, namely:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing strategic guidance and technical support to municipalities related to energy planning, energy efficiency and increase in the RES utilisation • Energy management guidance • SEAP development and monitoring • Organizing of Energy Info days
	The Zlín region is a NUTS III area, and there are many municipalities there with insufficient resources to prepare an inventory, action plans or well defined projects suitable to submit to existing national or European financial mechanisms etc. The role of the EAZK is to provide the know-how, experience and advice as a part of the regional governance to both region and municipalities to develop their own projects focused on RES and EE as well as to help them to develop their own SEAPs.
As far the energy policy of the region is concerned, EAZK plays the role of the facilitator and advisor in the communication between the region and the municipalities. EAZK also supports the region and the municipalities to gain financial sources from existing funds to develop their own energy action plans and projects on a basis of existing Energy strategy of the Zlín Region.	
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	www.eazk.cz
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	2006
End date:	Ongoing
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	EAZK acts as an independent advisor during the process of the development of these projects and action plans and finally the agency participates in implementation of the recommendations of these action plans. Since its establishment in 2006, Energy agency has initialized and developed more than 575 successful RES and energy efficiency projects in total value more than 180.000.000,- EUR on both local and regional level.
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	ManagEnergy
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	Zlín Energy agency successfully implementing SEAP [CZ] (europa.eu)

Table 3-18. Community Power for homes and businesses in Ireland.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Community Power for homes and businesses in Ireland.
Keywords:	Energy communities Renewable energy Governance structure
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	
Country:	Ireland
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Tipperary
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Community Power is Ireland's first community owned electricity supplier, and it is a partnership of community energy groups.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	Community Power is Ireland's first community owned electricity supplier. It is a partnership of community energy groups working for a sustainable energy future for Ireland which grew out of Ireland's first community owned wind farm, Templederry Wind Farm in Co Tipperary, and is now supplying electricity to homes and businesses all over Ireland. Community Power is working to deliver clean, renewable energy to homes and businesses in Ireland while empowering communities to own their own source of electricity and generate local jobs in rural communities.
Project full title / acronym:	Community Power
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	
Project website: (If applicable)	https://communitypower.ie/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	2000
End date:	ongoing
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Energy community self-organized by citizens and other entities or community groups. Now offering energy services for the energy transition.
References:	
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	

Table 3-19. Establishment of the European Community Power coalition.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Establishment of the European Community Power coalition.
Keywords:	Energy communities
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy communities
	Governance structure
	Multi-level governance
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	The Community Power Coalition brings together about 40 like-minded associations across Europe and is focused on empowering citizens on the energy generation and management.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	The Community Power Coalition brings together about 40 like-minded associations across Europe – representing energy cooperatives, networks of cities and local authorities, the renewable energy industry, legal experts, environmental NGOs and others. The Coalition is facilitated by Friends of the Earth Europe in Brussels.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	<p>Demands:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acknowledge citizen energy and renewable energy communities in national legislation through robust and clear definitions. 2. Strong inclusion of citizens and communities in national climate and energy planning. 3. Respect for new rights of self-consumers and energy communities, supported by a strong enabling framework at national level. 4. Ensure fair access for renewable energy communities to renewables support schemes. 5. Support a fair and inclusive energy transition, making sure no one is left behind. 6. Acknowledge value that energy citizens and communities can provide to the energy system. 7. Continued support from the European Institutions for energy communities at European level. 8. Capacity-building for local authorities to continue supporting community energy projects.
Project full title / acronym:	The European Community Power Coalition
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	European Commission (LIFE programme) European Climate Foundation, and the European Climate Initiative (EUKI) of the German Federal Ministry for the Environment Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU)
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://communitypowercoalition.eu/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	2021
End date:	ongoing
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	"Community Energy. A practical guide to reclaim power"
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://communitypowercoalition.eu/practical-handbook/

Table 3-20. Energy Citizenship and Energy Communities for a Clean Energy Transition.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Energy Citizenship and Energy Communities for a Clean Energy Transition
Keywords:	Energy communities
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
	Multi-level governance
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Public authorities' cooperation
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	Austria, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Spain
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	Arterra Bizimodu (Spain), Scalenghe (Italy), Groningen (Netherlands), Prusice (Poland)
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	An innovative research/approach to scale-up both energy citizenship and energy communities to achieve greater social acceptability and more durable governance arrangements.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	Methodology: At the core of the EC2 project is the empirical, quantitative assessment of energy citizenship and its relation to energy communities. However, this core is embedded within an interdisciplinary theoretical analysis and trans-disciplinary co-creation processes. The EC2 project will also work trans-disciplinarily by integrating perspectives and expertise from academia, stakeholders in the energy sector (energy providers, municipalities, distributors, aggregators), energy communities, and citizens. EC2 will gather data from citizens and energy communities across Europe and conduct several co-creation workshops along the different stages of the project in four in-depth regions in the Netherlands, Spain, Italy, and Poland, but also in Germany and Austria. Digital tools: EC ² will translate research into evidence-based innovative actions by co-creating (digital) tools for energy communities, by producing a digital training program, and by supplying actionable policy recommendations and practical advice.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Energy Citizenship and Energy Communities for a Clean Energy Transition / EC2
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
Project website: (If applicable)	https://ec2project.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	05/2021
End date:	04/2024 (Ongoing)
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	The project provides an interdisciplinary understanding of energy citizenship and the psychological, legal and economic factors supporting, or hindering, the emergence of citizens in energy communities. One of the outputs of the project will be a quantitative scale to assess the psychological manifestations of energy citizenship in individuals. Special attention is paid to the inclusivity in energy citizenship. The project studies the preferences and challenges of different social groups in becoming an energy citizen and joining an energy community. Communities, stakeholders, and citizens are engaged in the co-creation and evaluation of the tools developed in the project.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	(1) Interdisciplinary understanding of energy citizenship (ENG) https://ec2project.eu/sites/site0261/media/downloads/d2.1_interdisciplinary_understanding_of_energy_citizenship_2022_02_24_finalversion.pdf (2) Overview of available tools to support energy communities (ENG) https://online-raketen.at/sites/site0261/media/downloads/wp5_deliverable_5.1_final.pdf (3) Collaborative briefing, March 2023 "Are renewable energy communities a vehicle to mitigate the energy crisis and lift people out of energy poverty?" https://ec2project.eu/sites/site0261/media/downloads/collaborative-briefing-energy-communities-and-the-energy-crisis-2023.pdf

Table 3-21. Establishment of Minoan Energy Community in Crete.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Establishment of Minoan Energy Community in Crete.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Multi-level governance Renewable energy Governance structure Public authorities' cooperation Energy communities
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Greece
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Region of Crete / Municipality of Minoa Pediadas / Arkalohori
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Minoan Energy is a cooperative made up of private individuals and local businesses, which with the support of the Region of Crete and Municipalities-members of it, contests to be part of the energy transition from fossil fuels to RES, promoting at the same time the sustainability and socially inclusive economy.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	Minoan Energy Community has implemented already some very important projects towards energy transition. Among them is the project Sustainable Actions for Viable Energy (SAVE) funded by the Horizon 2020 project New Energy Solutions Optimised for Islands (NESOI) . The main tasks of the SAVE project are: a) the design of the technical solution, including geographical topology, for a smart grid within the geographical boundaries of the three Municipalities which had already become members of the Community at the moment of the proposal's submission (Municipalities of Minoa Pediadas, Archanon Asterousion and Viannou) and b) the final studies for the implementation of energy performance upgrade measures of the Municipal Sports Centre and the Indoor Sports Hall of Arkalochori. It has been nominated the first prize for LOCAL ENERGY ACTION for the European Sustainable Energy Awards of 2022 for its initiative to provide free energy to 200 households affected by the devastating earthquake of Sept 27, 2021. Recently, it announced one more excellence with a big project called Crete Valley submitted under the framework of the call for Energy Valleys of Horizon 2020, which forces the implementation of 13mil euro investment in RES projects in Crete.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Sustainable Actions for Viable Energy (SAVE) funded by the Horizon 2020
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Private and public funding
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://minoanenergy.com/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	10/2019
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	Ongoing
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Minoan Energy Community has developed a dynamic and evolving network of collaborators, recognising the importance of networking towards the attainment of its objectives. Key stakeholders of the energy community represent 4 different actors: Local Government (Municipalities and Regional) Academic Bodies, other Energy Communities and International Grids.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	https://compose.interreg-med.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Sites/Renewable_Energy/Projects/COMPOSE/What_we_achieve/WP5_Capitalisation/5.2.5_Policy_recommendations/5.2.5_PolicyRecommendations.pdf https://minoanenergy.com/en/#1615980779668-080178d3-fff4 https://nesoi.eu/system/files/private/nesoi/Brochures/nesoi_save_z-056_c.pdf https://minoanenergy.com/en/crete-valley/

Table 3-22. Governance in the Strategy for Energy Building Renovation in Asturias.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Governance in the Strategy for Energy Building Renovation in Asturias.
Keywords:	Governance structure
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Asturias
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Implementation of a Regional Strategy for the Energy Renovation of Buildings led by Asturias Energy Agency in Spain.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	Managed by the Regional Government of Asturias, Asturias Energy Agency (FAEN) is organizing the implementation of a Regional Strategy for the Energy Renovation of Buildings, which involves stakeholders from both the public and private sector. Public agents are responsible for the design, development and execution of the Strategy for the housing, energy and commercial sectors. The local administration and other key public institutions in the fields of construction and energy are also engaged in the implementation of the Strategy. With regards to the private sector, companies with technicians and professionals are involved in the energy rehabilitation process. In addition, there are professional associations and organizations with broad experience in reducing demand and improving energy consumption systems. The participation of energy trading companies and energy service companies is also essential.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	
Project website: (If applicable)	
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Month/year
End date:	Month/year OR Ongoing
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	For an effective public-private collaboration and an adequate governance and operability of the Strategy, it is imperative to define two instruments: roundtables and working groups, and the Regional Consultation Office. These are formed and organized in a coordinated manner according to the topics to be analysed.
References:	https://fedarene.org/best-practice/governance-in-the-strategy-for-energy-building-renovation-in-asturias/
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is	

Table 3-23. Kilkenny County Council Climate Change Adaptation Strategy 2019-2024

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Kilkenny County Council Climate Change Adaptation Strategy 2019-2024
Keywords:	Energy transition planning
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Governance structure
	Energy transition measures
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy communities
Country:	Ireland
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Kilkenny Town and County
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	This Climate Adaptation Strategy features a range of actions across the following sectors Energy and Buildings, Flood Resilience, Transport, Resource Management and Nature-Based Solutions and Communities.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	Climate Adaptation Strategy sets out the current climate change impacts and greenhouse gas emission levels in the county through the development of adaptation and mitigation baselines. This strategy examines the future impacts that climate change may have on Kilkenny and then sets out a first iteration of actions that will be used to reduce the source and effects of these impacts. The adaptation baseline has identified that the effects of climate change are already impacting on Kilkenny at a significant rate and are very likely to increase in their frequency and intensity. The mitigation baseline calculates the greenhouse gas emissions for the Council own activities and also for the entire county. It found that Kilkenny County Council produced 5,117 tonnes of CO2 in 2017. This strategy has been developed following an extensive process of research, policy analysis and workshops with staff, SPC and regional working groups. It follows on from the publication of Local Authority Adaptation Strategy Development Guidelines published in December 2018.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	
Project full title / acronym:	Kilkenny County Council Climate Change Adaptation Strategy 2019-2024
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	National funding
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	https://kilkennycoco.ie/eng/services/environment/strategy-plans-and-policies/climate-change-adaptation-strategy.pdf
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	October 2019
End date:	Ongoing
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	A 33% improvement in the councils' energy efficiency by 2020; A 40% reduction in the councils' greenhouse gas emissions by 2030.
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	https://kilkennycoco.ie/eng/services/environment/strategy-plans-and-policies/climate-change-adaptation-strategy.pdf
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	

Table 3-24. 8 Municipal Plans for Climate Action in the territory of Tâmega and Sousa (Portugal).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	8 Municipal Plans for Climate Action in the territory of Tâmega and Sousa (Portugal).
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning Energy transition measures Methodology / tool / solution Energy Efficiency in buildings Governance structure
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Portugal
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Baião, Castelo de Paiva, Celorico de Basto, Cinfães, Felgueiras, Marco de Canaveses, Penafiel, Resende.
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	This project began with the revisitation of the PIAAC-TS, and will culminate in the elaboration of the Intermunicipal Plan of Climate Action, with a view to updating information, but also to support, taking into account its vast information produced, the elaboration of the 8 (eight) Municipal Climate Action Plans (PMAC), one for each of the following Municipalities: Baião, Castelo de Paiva, Celorico de Basto, Cinfães, Felgueiras, Marco de Canaveses, Penafiel and Resende, fulfilling, in aggregate form, to the obligations provided for in paragraph 2 article 14 of the Climate Base Law.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].</i>	The territorial scope of the Municipal Climate Action Plans (PMAC) corresponds to the territory of Tâmega and Sousa. Thus, planning is defined according to the needs of the territory, taking as reference the local activity, the risks and vulnerabilities to climate change to which the territories will be subject, also identifying potential associated with climate change. The Action Plan considers a short-term approach (2030), but is geared towards meeting the P-BAC Adaptation by 2030 targets and the decarbonisation targets by 2050 set by PNEC 2030 and updated by the Climate Law: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by 2030, a reduction of at least 55 %; • by 2040, a reduction of at least 65 to 75 %; • By 2050, a reduction of at least 90 %. Climate action presupposes timely decision-making in the face of uncertainty and should be guided by: As part of the preparation of the PMAC mitigation component, the Reference Inventory of Energy Consumption and Carbon Dioxide (CO2) Emissions was prepared in order to quantify the energy consumption and CO2 emissions inherent to the activity developed in the Concelhos territories. The energy inventory includes the calculation of energy consumption and production (Final Energy Consumption Matrix and Local Energy Production Matrix), as well as the respective local evolutionary trends. The emissions inventory includes the analysis of greenhouse gas emissions, expressed in CO2eq. As part of the preparation of the PMAC, the impact and vulnerability assessment and respective climate risk are carried out, as well as the assessment of the adaptive capacity of the Concelhos territories. The adaptation component covers key sectors, as per the reference document "Guidelines for Regional Climate Action Plans, Climate Foundation Act" of 2022.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Portugal's Climate Base Law.
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	09/2023
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	02/2024
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Mitigation and adaptation measures for the region; Matrix of territorial actions, action sheets associated with respective cartography and associated action sheet; Macroeconomic impacts and cos benefits, costs of inaction; Just transition and resilient society.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	

Table 3-25. Municipal Energy Saving Plan for the Municipality of Baião (Portugal).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Municipal Energy Saving Plan for the Municipality of Baião (Portugal).
Keywords:	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Multi-level governance
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Portugal
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Municipality of Baião, District of Porto, Country Portugal
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Implementation of a plan/strategy with short and medium-term measures to reduce consumption and promote energy transition in the municipality.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	The Municipality of Baião, in compliance with Resolution of the Council of Ministers no. 82/2022, of 28/09, and in conjunction with the 11 municipalities of the Tâmega e Sousa Intermunicipal Community, defined an energy saving plan/strategy in the County. Some of the measures to be implemented in the short and medium term are: - Turn off exterior lighting in municipal buildings, - Reduce Christmas Lighting hours, - Regulate the temperatures and operating hours of air conditioning equipment, - Replace all exterior and interior lighting with LED lighting; - Invest in projects to use renewable energy; - Promote training - Resource Efficiency Program in Public Administration. These measures take into account the geopolitical crisis resulting from the conflict in Ukraine, with serious consequences for the European energy system, and the situation of severe drought throughout the continental territory, in the summer months, with cuts in hydroelectric energy.
Describe a best practice in the field of Governance practices & structures [e.g. a good example of a tool/method used for effective multi-level governance coordination between a Region and its Municipalities, as regards regional and local energy action plans; a good example of a permanent multi-level governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition at local/regional level; a good example of a public authority that demonstrates novel / effective implementation of multi-level governance; etc.].	
Project full title / acronym:	Resolution of the Council of Ministers No. 82/2022 - Defines preventive measures to address the current situation and possible future disruptions, to guarantee the security of energy supply
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	
Project website: (If applicable)	
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	12/2022
End date:	Ongoing
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Transition to green and renewable energy through the installation of photovoltaic panels in municipal buildings. Reduction of the municipality's energy bill. Address the current situation and possible future disruptions in energy supply as a result of geopolitical crises. Raising awareness among local authority employees and the general population.
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	https://www.cm-baião.pt/2022/12/09/municipio-de-baião-implementa-e-reforca-medidas-de-poupança-de-agua-e-de-energia/ https://greensavers.sapo.pt/baião-prepara-medidas-para-poupar-energia-e-agua-em-equipamentos-municipais/ https://novumcanal.pt/2022/12/baião/baião-implementa-medidas-de-poupança-de-agua-e-de-energia/
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	

4 Technical Best Practices and Solutions

This chapter records successful technical solutions. It includes cost-effective and innovative technical solutions to increase energy efficiency in public buildings, sustainable mobility solutions, and case studies of successful implementation of the above in actual projects.

Table 4-1. Integrated methodology & digital platform to support public authorities in energy-efficiency planning for public buildings.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Integrated methodology & digital platform to support public authorities in energy-efficiency planning for public buildings.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	Greece, Spain, France, Italy, Croatia, Bosnia & Herzegovina
Region / Municipality / location:	Municipalities of Heraklion (Greece), Elche (Spain), Cannes (France), Ravenna (Italy), Osijek (Croatia) and Mostar (Bosnia & Herzegovina).
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	An integrated methodology & digital platform to support MED public authorities in developing energy-efficiency action plans for public buildings.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	Methodology: An integrated methodology (composed of a series of Excel-based tools) was developed, to support public authorities in the MED area in the development of oriented action plans for energy efficiency of public buildings at local level. The methodology was developed to support public authorities in addressing the requirements of Article 7 of L.4342/2015 (Greek transposition of Article 5 of 2012/27/EU) on the exemplary role of public buildings and the need to conduct energy-efficiency action plans for public buildings. Digital platform: Excel-based user-friendly platform for data-base creation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for alternative retrofit scenarios for large samples of public buildings. The platform aims to facilitate public authorities in assessing the expected energy, environmental and economic implications of alternative retrofitting investments ranging from small-scale to deep interventions of energy upgrading for various public-building typologies.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Integrated Management Support for Energy Efficiency in Mediterranean Public Buildings / IMPULSE
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://impulse.interreg-med.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	11/2016
End date:	07/2019
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	By adopting the IMPULSE methodology, the 6 pilot Mediterranean Municipalities of Heraklion (Greece), Elche (Spain), Cannes (France), Ravenna (Italy), Osijek (Croatia) and Mostar (Bosnia & Herzegovina) completed a mature plan for gradual energy renovation projects in the next years. Using the IMPULSE platform, KPIs' databases for various retrofitting scenarios were produced for the 6 pilot Municipalities .
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	(1) IMPULSE methodology booklet (EN): https://impulse.interreg-med.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Sites/Efficient_Buildings/Projects/IMPULSE/D3.2.1_Booklet.pdf (2) Integrated public-buildings energy-efficiency plans for 6 pilot Mediterranean Municipalities: https://impulse.interreg-med.eu/what-we-achieve/deliverable-database/detail/?tx_elibrary_pi1%5Blivvable%5D=8456&tx_elibrary_pi1%5Baction%5D=show&tx_elibrary_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=Frontend%5CLivvable&cHash=b4ee8c0aa1d735a60a0c59869b410359 (3) IMPULSE building typologies and performance indicators platforms (4) Simulated results and hierarchy of retrofitting measures for Heraklion-Greece, url-ENG/GR

Table 4-2. Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings Roadmaps for coordinated regional & local strategies for improving the energy efficiency of public buildings.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings Roadmaps for coordinated regional & local strategies for improving the energy efficiency of public buildings.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures Energy Efficiency in buildings Methodology / tool / solution Energy transition planning Public authorities' cooperation
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Multiple countries Spain, Greece, Spain, Italy, Malta, Croatia
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Regions of Catalonia-Spain, Crete-Greece, Valencia-Spain, Emilia-Romagna-Italy, Lazio-Italy, Abruzzo-Italy, Gozo-Malta, Dubrovnik-Neretva- Croatia
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	Methodology - Tool: The project supported coordinated regional & local strategies for improving the energy efficiency of public buildings, through a shared information system, coordinated governance, training & financing strategies. The objective was to create integrated Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps, in a coordinated multi-governance level approach assessing the existing status and identifying actions for both Regional and Municipal buildings in the territory of Crete. Digital platforms: [1] SHERPA Shared Information System. Digital platform developed by CIMNE and used during the Testing (pilot) phase of the project, to facilitate the participating partner Regions in collecting, comparing, benchmarking, information for the energy consumption and energy saving measures for their public buildings. For the Region of Crete, information was entered in this platform for the 10 pilot Regional buildings assessed in the Testing phase. The platform is no longer operational by CIMNE. [2] SHERPA Capitalisation platform. An online platform developed by CRES (coordinator of SHERPA Capitalisation WP) as a "hub" of useful information available to all interested public authorities and stakeholders, operational beyond the end of SHERPA, including a searchable database of deliverables, best practices, tools, methodologies, from SHERPA and other relevant MED/EU projects and initiatives in the thematic of energy efficiency of buildings. Access to the platform is free. The platform is structured around 4 thematic Capitalisation Toolkits (Policy / Technical / Financial / Awareness), representing the holistic methodology introduced by the SHERPA project for addressing energy renovation of public buildings.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	SHared knowledge for Energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations - SHERPA
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	11/2016
End date:	10/2019
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	By adopting the SHERPA methodology, 8 Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps were developed, for the participating Mediterranean partner Regions.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC5YMSTW0-0zsEgww_6R2cHQ_ https://www.facebook.com/SHERPAMED

Table 4-3. Open source Big-Data Platform for collection, processing and exchanging energy data from different sources.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Open source Big-Data Platform for collection, processing and exchanging energy data from different sources.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Open source Big-Data Platform for collection, processing and exchanging energy data from different sources.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	A Big Data TOOL with AI will allow making decisions for de-risking investments in energy transition projects (in buildings). Initially will contain information from 4000 buildings of Generalitat of Catalonia. PLATFORM: an open source Big-Data reference Architecture for collection, processing and exchanging data from different sources.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Building Information aGGregation, harmonization and analytics platform/BIGG
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	H2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://www.bigg-project.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	1/12/2020
End date:	30/11/2023
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	BIGG is a 36-month project launched in December 2020. It demonstrates the application of big data technologies and data analytic techniques in the complete building life-cycle in more than 4000 buildings in 6 large-scale pilots, 3 in Spain (Catalonia) and 3 in Greece. As part of BIGG architecture, the project has developed an open, cloud-based, building-related data analytics toolbox that supports different data analysis techniques and is extensible to support third-party developments and a wide range of services.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	BIGG Web url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/ Catalan pilot url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/bigg-project-pilots-business-cases-and-use-cases/ Greek pilot url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/bigg-project-pilots-business-cases-and-use-cases-in-greece/

Table 4-4. One-stop shop digital platform tools to analyse and benchmark energy-efficiency measures for public buildings.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	One-stop shop digital platform tools to analyse and benchmark energy-efficiency measures for public buildings.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	Pilot sites in Spain and Bulgaria.
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	One-stop-shop digital platform to allow better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	The EN-TRACK platform will have several tools for different user levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • @General Public: Cross-sectional benchmarking tool to analyse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o @Energy Efficiency Measures: o @Building types • @Data providers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o @longitudinal benchmarking o @cross-sectional benchmarking
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings / EN-TRACK
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	H2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://en-track.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	01/11/2020
End date:	31/10/2023
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	Project website url-EN: https://en-track.eu/

Table 4-5. De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Methodology / tool / solution Energy transition measures Innovative financing Energy Efficiency in buildings
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Multiple countries
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Platform with open-source database for energy efficiency investments monitoring and benchmarking.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	The EEFIG De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DEEP is an open-source database for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking. • DEEP provides an improved understanding of the real risks and benefits of energy efficiency investments by providing market evidence and investment track records. • Includes 15,000+ energy efficiency projects in buildings and industry from 30 data providers. • New data and improved functionality is added regularly.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform / DEEP-EEFIG
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	European Commission's Directorate-General for Energy
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://deep.ec.europa.eu/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	EEFIG addresses barriers to energy efficiency financing through both policy design and market-based solutions to increase the scale of energy efficiency investments across Europe. Composed of over 300 representatives from more than 200 organisations, EEFIG's strength are its members - spanning public and private financial institutions, industry representatives and sector experts. EEFIG works through working groups that target specific themes. Through a multi-level stakeholder dialogue, working groups identify opportunities and barriers in the long-term financing for energy efficiency, and propose policy and market solutions.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	EEFIG web url-EN: https://ec.europa.eu/eefig/index_en DEEP web url-EN: https://ec.europa.eu/eefig/going-activities_en DEEP platform url-EN: https://deep.ec.europa.eu/

Table 4-6. Technical information on implemented case studies using biomass in 22 Municipalities in Girona.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Technical information on implemented case studies using biomass in 22 Municipalities in Girona
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Public authorities' cooperation Energy Efficiency in buildings Energy transition measures Renewable energy
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Spain
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Province of Girona
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Biomass implementation in 22 Municipalities in Girona: installation of 7 biomass boilers, 15 biomass heat networks and 2 forest biomass facilities.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	Each municipality details the project carried out with the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action Description Year of execution Cost of the investment, broken down by contribution of each governance structure Savings in CO2 emissions Energy savings Renewable energy production Percentage of energy savings
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Boilers, heat networks and facilities for chip production / Bebiomassgi
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	ERDF
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://www.ddgi.cat/web/servei/3372/calderes--xarxes-de-calor-i-instal-lacions-per-a-la-produccio-d-estella-operacio-go03-000003
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	Completed
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	The project has launched a new project called ForesHEAT, which provides online monitoring of forest biomass consumption. A free service to monitor and manage biomass installations for municipalities, biomass suppliers or energy service companies
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i>	Video results url-CAT: https://youtu.be/Lzf3V9YkFNA ForesHEAT url-CAT: https://www.forestheat.cat/

Table 4-7. Guide to facilitating the implementation of local energy communities in Girona.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Guide to facilitating the implementation of local energy communities in Girona.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy communities
	Renewable energy
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Province of Girona
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Biomass implementation in 22 Municipalities in Girona: installation of 7 biomass boilers, 15 biomass heat networks and 2 forest biomass facilities.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	The Girona Provincial Council has drawn up a guide to facilitate the implementation of local energy communities in the territory: Guide for the use of roofs and land for the local production of renewable energies.
Project full title / acronym:	Comunitats Locals d'Energia / Local Energy Communities
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Girona Provincial Council's Service Plan and Action Plan
Project website: (If applicable)	
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	90 projects of energy local communities already done or started a project.
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	Progress in 2022: 46 municipalities have initiated the drafting of these reports for the implementation of local energy communities and 27 more will start soon.
References:	Guide url-CAT
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	New guide launch url-CAT
	New project launch url-CAT

Table 4-8. On-line TOOL for a pre-check of EPC availability.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	On-line TOOL for a pre-check of EPC availability.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Innovative financing
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Online tool for a pre-check of EPC availability.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	Developed an on-line TOOL for a pre-check of EPC availability. Methodology is the EPC contract model developed. No tools for governance of ET projects. For a certain set of Public buildings, the governance is done directly by EPC facilitator's team of ICAEN.
Project full title / acronym:	
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Energy efficiency with Performance guarantees in the private and public sector (guarantEE).
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Horizon 2020 (2016-2019)
Project website: (If applicable)	https://guarantee-project.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	1/4/2016
End date:	31/3/2019
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	GuarantEE Precheck EPC tool: http://www.epccheck.eu/

Table 4-9. EPC model contracting to implement energy efficiency projects for public buildings.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	EPC model contracting to implement energy efficiency projects for public buildings.
Keywords:	Energy Efficiency in buildings
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Innovative financing
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	Implementation of energy efficiency projects in buildings based on EPC model contracting.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	The project was based on business models for energy efficiency implementation. The business models focused on different modalities of Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), to implement energy efficiency projects.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	
Project full title / acronym:	New finance for energy efficiency measures in Public Buildings / New Finance
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	Interreg MED 2014-2020
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://new-finance.interreg-med.eu/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	1/11/2016
End date:	30/4/2018
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Signed contracts under EPC model to finance energy efficiency measures in Croatia, Bosnia, Slovenia, Italy and Catalonia.
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	EPC guide
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	

Table 4-10. 4 key tools for energy transition at local level, through a Public-Private-Citizen-Partnership (PPCP).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	4 key tools for energy transition at local level, through a Public-Private-Citizen-Partnership (PPCP).
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Methodology / tool / solution Innovative financing Energy transition measures Governance structure
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Spain
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	City of Viladecans, Catalonia.
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Integration of 4 key tools for energy transition at local level, in Viladecans (Catalonia).
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	The innovative solution of PPCP tried to integrate 4 key tools for the energy transition: (ONE-LEVEL-GOVERNANCE) -Local energy operator (to supply and produce RES) -Local energy savings service operator (including innovative Energy Savings Contracting Model to capitalize energy savings) -Local energy investments operator (ESCO for deep energy renovation investments) -Local energy savings-based currency.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Innovative local public-private-citizen partnership for energy governance / Vilawatt
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	UIA (2016 – 2019)
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/viladecans
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	11/01/2016
End date:	31/10/2019
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	A mindset change in the local population, through enhanced knowledge and capacities related to energy transition and renovation of buildings. A new PPCP organization for energy governance that will empower and engage citizens, local administration and public sector for the energy transition. A deep renovation of 60 dwellings, supported by a participative scheme, and given high visibility.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i>	https://uia-initiative.eu/sites/default/files/2016-12/Viladecans%20-%20MEDIA%20-%20PPT%20presentation.pdf

Table 4-11. Knowledge Repository platform to support local and regional energy planning & Guidebook to Carbon Neutrality by 2050.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Knowledge Repository platform to support local and regional energy planning & Guidebook to Carbon Neutrality by 2050.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning
	Energy transition measures
	Multi-level governance
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Austria, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, Romania.
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Knowledge Repository platform to support local and regional energy planning & Guidebook to Carbon Neutrality by 2050.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	<p>C-Track 50 has gathered a number of inspiring multi-level governance examples and best practices across 11 EU countries and mapped the status quo of the policy planning processes at the national level to better understand the difficulties and challenges these may cause at the local level. These examples and best practices were collected via a questionnaire circulated among the national partners. The identified best practices cover a wide area of decarbonisation sectors – building retrofitting, energy plans, territorial development, energy efficiency, mobility- and include collaboration models in all levels of governance. Procedures applicable at each country level were thoroughly reviewed and discussed, during these national roundtables. Relevant recommendations on improving national priorities between national, regional and local authorities, especially in sight of the ambitious targets set on energy and climate policy planning at the EU level, have been produced and added to the final report as recommendations.</p> <p>The "Guidebook for achieving Carbon Neutrality by 2050" was developed as part of the H2020 project C-Track 50 and describes the key steps in the planning process, along with important considerations in each step. It also presents best practices to inspire cities and regions and help them better design actions to take forward in the decarbonisation process.</p> <p>The C-Track 50 Knowledge Repository is a dissemination portal including significant material that can support local and regional policy planning processes, as well as provide access to citizens to information regarding the implementation of energy improvement actions. To this end, EU strategic documents, national/regional energy and climate plans, legislative acts, as well as tools such as energy calculators for residences, and links to registries of certified technicians that can implement energy efficiency and renewable energy interventions have been included. The platform has been populated both with documents by partners for their respective countries and with EU documents and it is accessible in 10 languages, besides English.</p>

Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	C-TRACK 50
Funding Programme: <i>(if applicable)</i>	Horizon 2020
Project website: <i>(if applicable)</i>	https://www.c-track50.eu
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	<p>C-Track 50 employed an innovative approach in empowering regional/local authorities, by building their capacity and addressing barriers in energy planning, as well as enabling them to actively contribute to the EU's long term energy policy targets, by introducing the carbon neutrality concept at regional/local level, ensuring at the same time multi governance collaboration at all levels to facilitate the planning process.</p> <p>In conclusion, C-Track 50 applied this innovative approach and engaged national and sub-national authorities in eleven (11) countries, and as a result it:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitated the development and implementation of one hundred and seven (107) integrated sustainable energy and climate resilient plans at a local level, • Provided recommendations/facilitated the development of eleven (11) integrated sustainable energy and climate resilient plans at a regional level and, • Provided recommendations for establishing new/revising existing energy and climate policies at a national level, in line with the carbon neutrality target by 2050.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is available)</i>	<p>Existing Multi-level Governance Models in 11 EU Countries: https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/Briefing_paper_final.pdf Putting Regions on Track for Carbon Neutrality by 2050 - Final Publishable Report - November 2021 https://c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/2021/Final%20Publishable%20Report%20%28%29.pdf Energy Planning Process Report in 11 EU Countries: https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/View%20Report.pdf Guidebook for achieving Carbon Neutrality by 2050 https://c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/2021-06/Guidebook_for_Achieving_Carbon_Neutrality_by_2050.pdf Recommendations on national energy priorities in the eleven participating countries https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/C-Track50_Del_D2_5.pdf C-Track 50 Knowledge Repository: https://www.c-track50.eu/knowledge-repository</p>

Table 4-12. Database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Multi-level governance
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance between regional and local level for sustainable energy action planning.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	COOPENERGY fostered a more collaborative approach between regional and local public authorities for more cohesion in the design and implementation of their respective sustainable energy action plans. COOPENERGY developed a database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe as well as a guidebook with a step-by-step approach on how to implement multi-level governance.
Project full title / acronym:	
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	COOPENERGY
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Intelligent Energy Europe
Project website: (If applicable)	https://fedarene.org/project/coopenenergy/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	 www.coopenenergy.eu
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	Coopenenergy – A guide to Multi-level Governance for local and regional public authorities https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/151202-FINAL-Coopenenergy-Guidebook.pdf COOPENERGY – 60 best practices on MLG collaboration for sustainable energy planning: COOPENERGY – 60 best practices on MLG collaboration for sustainable energy planning: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/Final-60-BPs-compressed.pdf
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly	

Table 4-13. Technical tools of Regional Observatories to inform local and regional energy transition policies and monitor their implementation.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Technical tools of Regional Observatories to inform local and regional energy transition policies and monitor their implementation.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning
	Public authorities' cooperation
	Energy transition measures
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	Technical tools of Regional Observatories to inform local and regional energy transition policies and monitor their implementation.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	Observatories of the Data4action all have tools to inform local and regional energy transition policies (data collection, data monitoring, data visualisation and exchanges with local authorities) and monitor their implementation on their territories.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	
Project full title / acronym:	DATA4ACTION
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	Intelligent Energy Europe
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://fedarene.org/project/data4action/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	Completed
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Within the Data4Action project, 4 Regional Energy Observatories: Oreges Rhône Alpes (FR), Energieluppen of Norrbotten (SE), Ligurian Energy and Environment Observatory (IT) & Climate Observatory Nord-Pas de Calais (FR) have supported the creation of 7 new ones in Alba (RO), Carlow Kilkenny (IE), Torino (IT), Plovdiv (BG), Zlin (CZ), Kent (UK) and Greece.
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	Data4Action – Energy data sharing for sustainable energy planning:
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D4A_final-publishable-report.pdf
	Data4Action – Policy recommendations on improving energy data sharing for effective energy planning at sub-national levels:
	https://fedarene.org/publication/policy-recommendations-on-improving-energy-data-sharing-for-effective-energy-planning-at-sub-national-levels/
	Data4Action – Data Access Guidebook for SEAPs:
	https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/valide-16-04-2017D4A-6.2_Leaflet_EU.pdf
	Data4Action – Project Leaflet:
	https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/valide-16-04-2017D4A-6.2_Leaflet_EU.pdf

Table 4-14. Heraklion 2030 Climate Neutral & Smart City.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Heraklion 2030 Climate Neutral & Smart City.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
	EU funding
	Energy transition measures
Country:	Greece
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	Municipality of Heraklion, Crete
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Support tools available to Municipality of Heraklion through its participation in the EU 100 Intelligent Cities Challenge.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	With their participation in this EU initiative, 100 EU cities are expected to have access to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailor-made advice and assistance from the Mission Platform (managed by the NetZeroCities consortium); • Unlocking additional funding and financing opportunities through a Mission label; • Research & innovation funding opportunities for cities to join large innovation actions, pilot projects and demonstrations (total budget from Horizon Europe for 2021-2023 is €360 million); • Support through a national coordination network Networking opportunities, learning and exchange of experiences among cities; • Support with involving citizens in decision-making High visibility – raised political profile and attractiveness for investment and skilled workers
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative. a private initiative etc.	Heraklion 2030 "Climate-Neutral & Smart City"
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Horizon Europe (2021-2027)
Project website: (If applicable)	https://mission100.heraklion.gr/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	Heraklion Municipality was not included in the 10 EU cities selected in April 2022 but in light of the overwhelming interest from 377 cities to join the mission, the Commission is putting in place support for cities that were not selected, including support through the Mission Platform and funding opportunities under the Cities Mission Work Programme of Horizon Europe.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_2591 https://www.intelligentcitieschallenge.eu/cities/heraklion

Table 4-15. Promotion of zero-pollutant vehicles in the Greece and Cyprus cooperation area.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Promotion of zero-pollutant vehicles in the Greece and Cyprus cooperation area.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures Energy Efficiency in buildings Methodology / tool / solution Energy transition planning
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Multiple countries Greece, Cyprus
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Promotion of zero-pollutant vehicles in the Greece and Cyprus cooperation area.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	An innovative element was the introduction of zero-pollutant vehicles that will be used by both the local population and visitors as well as by people with disabilities. The creation of a system within urban areas with remarkable tourist traffic, which are characterized by high levels of air pollution such as the project area, will have the effect of rebuilding a quality living standard for residents and visitors in a healthy and clean environment. Promotion of means and modes of transport (electric vehicles) within the historical center of Municipalities participating in the project with zero environmental footprint and less noise than conventional. In particular, the Municipality of Heraklion: -Procured 2 electric buses of small size and pilot operation on two routes in the historical center; -Prepared a Study of routes to historic sites setting up bus stops oriented towards the emergence of cultural and historical monuments; -Developed a web-based application that allows real-time information, whether via the Internet or via mobile phones, to allow actual arrivals and departures to be based on a GPS system and real-time information to be available about the closest stops and the total route of the electric buses, as well as a telematics system where, via electronic signs located at each stop - historic site, the visitor is informed about the arrival of the bus and the historical data concerning the location.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	ECOROUTS
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Interreg Greece-Cyprus 2014-2020
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://mission100.heraklion.gr/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	Completed (2021)
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	https://ecorouts-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Project-ECOROUTS_English.pdf https://flashnews.gr/post/459199/hrakleio-prasines-kai-prosbasimes-diadromes-gia-olovs/

Table 4-16. Improvement of water networks in 6 Municipalities in Crete.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Improvement of water networks in 6 Municipalities in Crete.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning
Country:	Greece
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Region of Crete
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Improvement of water networks in 6 Municipalities in Crete.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	Expanding automation to new local stations and upgrading local automation control stations (SCADA). The reduction of water leakages is expected to have a positive impact in water and energy saving since in most cases, the operation of water pumps is the most energy consuming infrastructure in all Greek Municipalities.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Telemetry & remote-control of leaks in new water networks, expanding automation to new local stations and upgrading local automation control stations (SCADA)
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Greece National Operational program for Transport Infrastructure, Environment and Sustainable Development) of the NSRF 2014-2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/EN/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/greece/2014gr16m1op001
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Rational management of water resources and improvement of the quality of water stock while reducing leaks.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://government.gov.gr/88-6-ekat-evro-stous-ota-gia-tin-anavathmisi-ton-diktion-idrefsis-ke-ton-periorismo-ton-diarroon/

Table 4-17. Methodology of project categorization and templates with Technical Specifications, for energy upgrade projects in public buildings in Crete.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Methodology of project categorization and templates with Technical Specifications, for energy upgrade projects in public buildings in Crete.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Greece
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Region of Crete
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Methodology of project categorization and templates with Technical Specifications, for energy upgrade projects in public buildings in Crete.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	Assignment of expertise for energy upgrade projects, from which a methodology of project categorization was defined and templates with Technical Specifications were prepared that cover all potential systems (as described in page 150 of the annual report included in References below).
Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	
Project full title / acronym:	Actions of Energy Upgrading and Energy Saving (EE) and Utilization of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in Sports Facilities
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme:	Greek National Operational Program "Transport Infrastructure, Environment and Sustainable Development" and Regional Operational Program of Crete 2014-2020
(If applicable)	
Project website:	http://www.rethymno.gr
(If applicable)	
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	Ongoing
End date:	
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	Annual implementation report: https://ymeperaa.gr/images/Implementation_report_2014GR16M1OP001_2020_0_el.pdf Indicative study for the sports centre in Chania Municipality: https://www.chania.gr/files/55/44814/06_tehniki_ekthesi_naytathlitikoy_soydas_signed.pdf?rnd=1637663502 Programme information
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports/photos/videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly	

Table 4-18. Common methodology for the preparation of Energy Efficiency Investment Plans in more than 70 public authorities in the MED area.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Common methodology for the preparation of Energy Efficiency Investment Plans in more than 70 public authorities in the MED area.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
	Energy transition measures
	Public authorities' cooperation
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Common methodology and 70 public authorities engaged for the preparation of energy efficiency investments.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	Within the STEPPING project a common methodology was identified. More than 70 public authorities were engaged thanks to local events and a technical assistance service provided, for the preparation of energy efficiency investments. For the purpose, 22 Formal Agreements were signed. Small municipalities of a specific area were pooled together to develop Joint Investment Plans (economy of scale plus critical mass for the EPC market requirements) and, in some cases, to launch the EPC tender. After the selection of 170 suitable buildings an energy audit campaign was carried on, back to back with training activity in each of the regions involved. The common working approach, schemes and tools developed by the project partners allowed the drafting of 16 Investment Plans, tailored to the different framework conditions of the territories. Their implementation would bring to a total investment of about 18,5 M€ with an energy saving of 7 GWh/year and about 2000 t of CO2/year avoided emission. Thanks to a wide involvement of policy makers and stakeholders STEPPING released the "EPC Policy recommendations" and all the experience gained during the project implementation, together with an analysis of the specificity of the MED Area, was resumed in the EPC MED Guidelines. This document provides extremely useful advises to all the subjects interested in replicating and improving the STEPPING lessons learnt. Despite the existence of some technical issues (i.e. the climatic specificity of the MED Area, the level of maturity of the market, the financial framework conditions) and several political and administrative bottlenecks, the main goals of the project were achieved even more than expected.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.	STEPPING
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://stepping.interreg-med.eu/
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	January 2016
End date:	October 2019
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	STEPPING PLUS is an On-going project that started in March 2021.
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	70 public authorities engaged; 22 Formal Agreements signed; 16 Investment Plans drafted; EPC Policy recommendations released.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).	One of the key deliverables of STEPPING is the MED EPC Guidelines aiming to provide step-by-step guidance for the energy retrofitting of public buildings in the MED area through the use of Energy Performance Contracts, taking into consideration the intrinsic characteristics of the region: https://aegean-energy.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/med-guidelines.pdf

Table 4-19. Energy management for institutions established by the Zlín Region and for Municipalities of the Zlín Region

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Energy management for institutions established by the Zlín Region and for Municipalities of the Zlín Region
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Czech Republic
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Zlín Region and municipalities of the Zlín Region
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	One-stop-shop providing energy management for 86 institutions of the Zlín Region and more than 40 municipalities of the Zlín Region.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions (e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.)</i>	<p>The Energy Agency monitors and evaluates energy management data in 86 organizations established in the Zlín Region, of which 13 are from the social services sector, 68 are from the education sector, 1 is from the healthcare sector and 4 are from the culture sector. This obligation was approved by the Council of the Zlín Region on October 8, 2007.</p> <p>In addition, EAZK currently records energy management for selected buildings in 40 municipalities of the Zlín region. The monitoring centre is operated as a part of the EAZK and has become the official tool through which it is possible to monitor and more effectively implement the Energy Concept of the Zlín Region, regional SEAP and SEAPs of particular municipalities.</p> <p>Data monitoring tool has been developed on a basis of MS Access software and external delivery of user oriented super-structure linked to existing baseline data inventory on monthly temperatures, electricity, natural gas and hot and cold water consumption in order to create an integral and user friendly energy data processing tool.</p> <p>Although some parts of the system were done externally, all proceedings possible to be done by core EAZK staff were done internally. The result is a unique tool respecting both the needs of EAZK and its monitoring centre as well as the needs for flexible and user friendly application for monitoring and evaluation of consumption of different energy carriers.</p>
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://www.eazk.cz/article/energeticky-management-priklad-z-praxe-stredni-skola-copt-zlin
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	2007
End date:	ongoing
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	One-stop-shop providing energy management for 86 institutions of the Zlín Region and more than 40 municipalities of the Zlín Region since 2007
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	(1) EAZK www.eazk.cz

Table 4-20. Enhancing energy efficiency in public buildings in Central Europe by offering best practices, databases of contractors and appliances, financial expertise and a 3D Energy Management System in OnePlace platform.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Enhancing energy efficiency in public buildings in Central Europe by offering best practices, databases of contractors and appliances, financial expertise and a 3D Energy Management System in OnePlace platform.
Keywords:	Energy transition planning
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition measures
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Innovative financing
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	Italy, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Croatia, Poland, Hungary, Austria
Region / Municipality / location:	Emilia-Romagna region (Italy), municipality of Velenje (Slovenia), city of Koprivnica (Croatia), municipality of Judenburg (Austria), Upper Styria (Austria), municipality of Tolna (Hungary), Mazovia (Poland), Zlin Region (Czech Republic)
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description:	Development and implement of technical solutions, strategies, management approaches & financing schemes to achieve higher Energy Efficiency in public buildings through a transnational cooperation.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • training events related to EE actions and solutions, offered in the partnership countries, with more than 200 participants.
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	

<p>Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i></p>	<p>Boosting Energy Efficiency in Central European Cities through Smart Energy Management (BOOSTEE-CE)</p>
<p>Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i></p>	<p>Interreg Central Europe</p>
<p>Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i></p>	<p>https://programme2014-20.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/BOOSTEE-CE.html</p>
<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	<p>The image shows the logo for Interreg Central Europe BOOSTEE-CE, which includes the text 'Interreg CENTRAL EUROPE' and 'BOOSTEE-CE' next to the European Union flag. Below the text is a green circular logo with a white stylized plant or leaf symbol. To the right of the logo is a photograph of a city with many buildings that have blue roofs, likely representing the project's focus on energy efficiency in public buildings.</p>
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>01/2017</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>05/2020</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>The partnership developed and implemented technical solutions, strategies, management approaches & financing schemes to achieve higher Energy Efficiency (EE) in public buildings in partners' regions and municipalities. This was achieved through a transnational cooperation and using geospatial data, smart energy management tools and energy audits to facilitate the implementation of EE buildings. The final aim is to improve the governance of EE in existing public buildings (within Pilot Actions) and ultimately reduce energy consumption.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i></p>	<p>(1) The Online Energy Platform - OnePlace (Interreg Central Europe site) https://programme2014-20.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/WP2-results-and-documents.html (2) The Online Energy Platform - OnePlace https://oneplace.fbk.eu/</p>

Table 4-21. The conceptual approach to the energy efficiency in large hospital area in the Zlín Region with the support from OP Environment

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	The conceptual approach to the energy efficiency in large hospital area in the Zlín Region with the support from OP Environment.
Keywords:	Energy Efficiency in buildings Renewable energy EU funding
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	
Country:	Czech Republic
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Zlín Region
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Several consequent and interlinked investment projects on RES and energy efficiency leading to a considerable decrease of the energy demand in a large hospital area in Uherské Hradiště.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	<p>Hospital in Uherské Hradiště is one of four hospitals belonging to the Zlín Region. The individual pavilions of the hospital were in a very poor condition from the energy point of view: high heat consumption, overheating in summer etc. The heat and hot water sources in the central boiler room were old and inefficient and all this led to large heat losses.</p> <p>Between 2012 and 2020 Energy Agency of the Zlín Region initiated, developed, and administered a set of several consequent investment projects on RES and energy efficiency leading to a considerable decrease of the energy demand in a large hospital area in Uherské Hradiště with the support from OP Environment Among measures implemented in this period belong:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reconstruction of the central boiler room and area heat distribution, including the installation of 2 pieces of solar panels for the preparation of hot water, - Complex insulation of 6 hospital pavilions, - Complex heat insulation of 2 hostels for hospital staff, - Photovoltaic power plants on the 3 central buildings roofs with combined installed power 219 kWp. <p>Investments undertaken significantly reduced both heating and operational costs of the hospital and thus saved public funds spent on operations in health care. The installation of PV panels increased the hospital's self-sufficiency and reduced electricity consumption from non-renewable sources. Thanks to the insulation and installation of air conditioning with recuperation, the internal microclimate of the building was improved.</p> <p>Methodical management of energy management is provided by the Energy agency of the Zlín Region because only a proper implementation of energy management ensures all measures being fully operational.</p>
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	
Project website: (If applicable)	

<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>2012</p>
<p>End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	<p>2019</p>
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual total heat savings for all implemented measures combined are 44,828.59 GJ and annual CO2 reductions achieved are 2,999.44 tons. • Total implementation costs combined were 5.486.000 EUR with the contribution from the OP Environment in amount 1.878.000 EUR . • A pleasant environment is created in the hospital contributing to the well-being of all users, which is so important in their treatment process.
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i></p>	<p>(1) FEDARENE https://fedarene.org/best-practice/conceptual-approach-to-energy-efficiency-in-large-hospital-area-in-the-zlin-region/</p>

Table 4-22. "Local Energy Communities: «Centrales Villageoises»: a Local Citizen-owned Energy Communities' Success Story"

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Local Energy Communities: «Centrales Villageoises»: a Local Citizen-owned Energy Communities' Success Story.
Keywords:	Energy communities
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Public authorities' cooperation
	Multi-level governance
	Renewable energy
Country:	France
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	AURA-EE - Auvergne Rhône-Alpes Region, France
Short description:	
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	In 2010, Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Energie Environnement (AURA-EE) together with 5 natural regional Parks initiated an experimental project named "Centrales Villageoises" whose model is now spreading throughout France. The objective of this experimental project was to put renewable energy production projects at the service of the development of rural territories.
Long description:	
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	From 2010 to 2014, the experimentation was piloted on 8 pilot sites and progressively led to the elaboration of local citizen-owned companies which developed and financed some first PV plants. The entire technical, legal and financial framework was then consolidated and enabled the concept to be replicated on other sites. In 2018, with the support of AURA-EE, the Association of Centrales Villageoises was created in order to further expand and support the model in France. The association provides one-stop shop services to the communities through framework agreements established with various companies (insurances, banks, engineering companies, DSO,...). AURA-EE works in close cooperation with the association in order to develop additional services. The Centrales Villageoises local companies all abide by a charter. First, their governance is mainly driven by citizens who forge links with local municipalities. Their activities have to be consistent with the local public policies. In addition, they generate local benefits and contribute to the development of their territory. They also use a shared approach with common tools and services and share their experience to improve collectively the network's technical resources. Last but not least, they behave in a supportive way and bring assistance to each other.

<p>Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i></p>	
<p>Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i></p>	
<p>Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i></p>	<p>https://www.centralesvillageoises.fr/centrales-villageoises-local-citizen-owned-energy-communities</p>
<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	<p>Inauguration of the Centrale Villageoise of 4 Montagnes (Vercors). © Centrales Villageoises</p>
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>2010</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>2014</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>In August 2021, 57 territories are currently involved and there are more than 350 PV installations in operation, operated by 32 Centrales Villageoises companies and €11 million already been invested. The 350 installations represent an installed capacity of 4.8 MWp and an annual production of 5.4 GWh.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i></p>	

Table 4-23. EKIOLA: Prosumer PV Cooperatives in the Basque Country

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	EKIOLA: Prosumer PV Cooperatives in the Basque Country.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy communities Training seminars Energy transition measures Innovative financing
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Spain
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Basque Country
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	EKIOLA is a public-private initiative promoted by the Company KREAN and the Basque Energy Agency (EVE) that is leading the creation of prosumer power cooperatives in the Basque Country through agreements with municipalities and citizens.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	Interested municipalities will be responsible of selecting the appropriate site for the PV plant, implementing the building projects, managing all the administrative requirements and supporting the citizens that wish to take part in the project. The participation of local private stakeholders such as financial institutions and banks to finance the projects is also expected. The citizens will be prioritised as members of the energy community that will be also open to the participation of local administration and business. Each member of the energy community will cover 100% of the electricity demand from a local PV plant. Thus each participant will purchase only the PV panels required to meet the demand. The minimum required participants to develop an energy community under the EKIOLA initiative is 400 citizens. This represents the involvement of 12,000 to 20,000 families by 2024.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://fedarene.org/best-practice/ekiola-prosumer-pv-cooperatives-in-the-basque-country/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	2021
End date:	2024
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	30 to 50 non-profit cooperative energy communities will be established, which will have a live period of, at least, 25 years. The development of this initiative means the recognition of the important role of citizens in driving the energy transition and so aims to put consumers at the heart of the energy transition by converting them into Prosumers that will participate in the generation and management PV power stations between 1 and 5 MW. Each power cooperative will build and operate PV parks that will produce energy according to the demand required by the cooperative members. The new solar PV plants will be installed in urban areas, producing Km0 renewable electricity. These plants will have a size of 1 MW to 5 MW. This means an investment between €800,000 and €4 million in each of the energy communities, depending on the land price.

Table 4-24. Multiple Impacts Calculation Tool

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Multiple Impacts Calculation Tool
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Public lighting
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Estonia, Spain
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Municipality of Calvià (Spain), Municipality of Tartu (Estonia), Municipality of Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain)
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	A comprehensive approach and user-friendly online tool to estimate the multiple impacts or multiple benefits of energy efficiency measures.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	Methodology: MICAT's methodological approach was built on existing concepts for quantifying energy efficiency impacts and the role of the Multiple Impacts of Energy Efficiency. Previous research has revealed that a wide range of impacts occur in tandem with an increase in energy efficiency when energy efficiency measures are implemented. They can be categorised into three main categories: social (health benefits or poverty alleviation), environmental (energy savings and reduced GHG emissions) and economic impacts (positive macro-economic impacts on economic growth, employment, innovation and competitiveness). The assessment of Multiple Impacts of Energy Efficiency measures within MICAT also followed these categories. Digital platform: The back-end of the MICAT Tool consists of different modules, which cover different general functions. The front-end builds the bridge to the user of the tool by providing the common user interface and the tools to analyse and display results calculated by the modules in the back-end.
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Multiple Impacts Calculation Tool / MICAT
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://micatool.eu/micat-project-en/

<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>10/2020</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>11/2023</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>A MICATool Pilot Cities worked with the MICAT project team in a structured collaboration process to co-develop and explore the Multiple Impacts Calculation Tool's efficacy in the context of the Pilot City's local sustainability, energy efficiency, and/or climate action planning processes.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i></p>	<p>(1) MICAT booklet (ENG): https://micatool.eu/micat-project-wAssets/docs/publications/MICAT_Brochure_Multiple_Impacts_Calculation_Tool.pdf</p> <p>(2) MICAT Overall quantification and monetisation concept (ENG): https://micatool.eu/micat-project-wAssets/docs/publications/reports/MICAT_D2-1_quantification_concept.pdf</p> <p>(3) MICAT Cost-Benefit Analysis and aggregation methodology (ENG): https://micatool.eu/micat-project-wAssets/docs/publications/reports/MICAT_D2-2_cost_benefit_analysis.pdf</p>

Table 4-25. C-IZEBs (Cooperative Intelligent education & electromobility Zero Energy Buildings)

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	C-IZEBs (Cooperative Intelligent education & electromobility Zero Energy Buildings)
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Greece, Cyprus
Region / Municipality / location:	Municipality of Heraklion (Greece), University of Cyprus and Ministry of Education of Cyprus - case study in the Municipality of Lefkosia (Secondary school of Platy Aglatzias)
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	The C-IZEBs project aims to create intelligent school complexes that will be energy upgraded to meet the need for reduced energy consumption in both countries in the public sector, in order to comply with EU guidelines.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	A Model of Almost Zero Buildings Consumption took place, which transformed them into "Intelligent" with the use of technological equipment and the Living Labs application, and into "Green", with the addition of characteristics related to the activity of buildings. Living Labs, ie the live workshops / participatory learning platforms of users of intelligent green buildings, are the modernity of the project and emphasize its ability to utilize existing practices in the field of the program, and to go beyond them. The selected buildings are two school units, in which the project seeks a) to reduce energy consumption, b) to optimize the sense of comfort, c) to enhance sustainable mobility, by creating electric charging stations for vehicles and d) to carry out participatory training to strengthen existing actions (teaching / learning) and to ensure the sustainability of outcomes. Beneficiary administrations face common challenges in their commitments to the EU (meeting the Europe 2020 targets) and the citizens of the eligible area. The pilot actions directly benefit the study area, and their outflows are visible immediately after the upgrade / intervention in the two buildings.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	
Project full title / acronym:	C-IZEBs (Cooperative Intelligent education & electromobility Zero Energy Buildings)
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	Interreg Greece- Cyprus 2014-2020
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://cizebs.eu/en/the-program/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	

Progress status - Start date:	11/2021
End date:	10/2023
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Remote monitoring of the energy efficiency of buildings, Enhancing sustainable mobility through the creation of charging stations for electric vehicles and bicycles. Exchange of know-how in studies related to the energy design of buildings (including RES issues) through the energy upgrade of existing infrastructure. A manual that includes the results of the energy upgrades of the buildings. Raising public awareness.
References:	
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://cizebs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/%CE%A0%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%B1%CE%B4%CE%BF%CF%84%CE%AD%CE%BF-3.2.3-%CE%A4%CE%95%CE%A7%CE%9D%CE%99%CE%9A%CE%97-%CE%9C%CE%95%CE%9B%CE%95%CE%A4%CE%97-%CE%95%CE%9D%CE%95%CE%A1%CE%93%CE%95%CE%99%CE%91%CE%9A%CE%97%CE%A3-%CE%91%CE%9D%CE%91%CE%92%CE%91%CE%98%CE%9C%CE%99%CE%A3%CE%97%CE%A3-%CE%9A%CE%A4%CE%99%CE%A1%CE%99%CE%A9%CE%9D-%CE%9A%CE%91%CE%99-%CE%9C%CE%95%CE%A4%CE%91%CE%A4%CE%A1%CE%9F%CE%A0%CE%97%CE%A3-%CE%A4%CE%9F%CE%A5%CE%A3-%CE%A3%CE%95-%CE%95%CE%A5%CE%A6%CE%A5%CE%97.pdf

Table 4-26. Biomass district heating network in Roses.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Biomass district heating network in Roses.
Keywords:	Renewable energy
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Roses (Spain)
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Biomass district heating network in Roses
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	The aim of this project is to install two biomass boilers of 300 kW each to supply hot water for heating and hot sanitary water to the buildings of the Municipal Swimming Pool, the Sports Hall and the "Mas Oliva" Municipal Stadium. The project has also taken into account the possible future expansion of the thermal demand in the following buildings in the reservation of the spaces and in the dimensioning of the pipe of the main line of the network: Llar d'Infants "El Franquet", Escola Jaume Vicens You live, Montserrat Vayreda School, "La Vinyassa" Municipal Camp and Els Grecs School.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Biomass district heating network in Roses
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Horizon 2020
Project website: (If applicable)	
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	07/2018
End date:	07/2019
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	By installing two biomass boilers of 300 kW each we can supply hot water for heating and hot sanitary water to the buildings of the Municipal Swimming Pool, the Sports Hall and the "Mas Oliva" Municipal Stadium
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.	

Table 4-27. Replacement of lighting with LED technology in the municipality of Aiguaviva.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION																																																																															
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS																																																																														
TITLE:	Replacement of lighting with LED technology in the municipality of Aiguaviva																																																																														
Keywords:	Energy transition measures																																																																														
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Public lighting Innovative financing																																																																														
Country:	Spain																																																																														
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.																																																																															
Region / Municipality / location:	Aiguaviva (Spain)																																																																														
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).																																																																															
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	An integrated methodology & digital platform to support MED public authorities in developing energy-efficiency action plans for public buildings.																																																																														
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	<p>8 managment box 495 lightig points 524 luminaires Before Nominal Power = 69,893 kW After Nominal Power = 25,787 kW</p> <p>Total investment €195,246.50 63.84% reduction in energy consumption Savings of €12,489/year Emission reduction of 46.79 Tn CO2eq/year</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>NIQUADRE</th> <th>PUNTS DE LLUM</th> <th>LUMINÀRIES</th> <th>POTENCIA (w)</th> <th>POT. PROP (w)</th> <th>PRESSUPOST</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Total 1</td> <td>87</td> <td>87</td> <td>4802</td> <td>2357</td> <td>27.300,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 2</td> <td>10</td> <td>16</td> <td>7600</td> <td>2850</td> <td>4.500,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 3</td> <td>66</td> <td>75</td> <td>11651</td> <td>4565</td> <td>22.900,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 4</td> <td>89</td> <td>97</td> <td>16450</td> <td>5330</td> <td>28.850,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 5</td> <td>32</td> <td>32</td> <td>2700</td> <td>1285</td> <td>13.100,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 6</td> <td>90</td> <td>92</td> <td>13500</td> <td>4500</td> <td>27.000,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 7</td> <td>117</td> <td>117</td> <td>12250</td> <td>4600</td> <td>35.100,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 8</td> <td>4</td> <td>8</td> <td>340</td> <td>140</td> <td>2.400,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total 9</td> <td>4</td> <td>4</td> <td>600</td> <td>160</td> <td>2.400,00 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total general substitució luminàries</td> <td>491</td> <td>516</td> <td>69893</td> <td>25787</td> <td>170.480,00 €</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>La taula següent mostra el cost del terme fix de potència i l'establí assolit per quadre:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>QUADRE</th> <th>Importa TP (en k€) (K)</th> <th>Nov Import TP</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>SUBTOTAL QUADRE 1</td> <td>347</td> <td>102</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SUBTOTAL QUADRE 2</td> <td>459</td> <td>126</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SUBTOTAL QUADRE 3</td> <td>213</td> <td>187</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	NIQUADRE	PUNTS DE LLUM	LUMINÀRIES	POTENCIA (w)	POT. PROP (w)	PRESSUPOST	Total 1	87	87	4802	2357	27.300,00 €	Total 2	10	16	7600	2850	4.500,00 €	Total 3	66	75	11651	4565	22.900,00 €	Total 4	89	97	16450	5330	28.850,00 €	Total 5	32	32	2700	1285	13.100,00 €	Total 6	90	92	13500	4500	27.000,00 €	Total 7	117	117	12250	4600	35.100,00 €	Total 8	4	8	340	140	2.400,00 €	Total 9	4	4	600	160	2.400,00 €	Total general substitució luminàries	491	516	69893	25787	170.480,00 €	QUADRE	Importa TP (en k€) (K)	Nov Import TP	SUBTOTAL QUADRE 1	347	102	SUBTOTAL QUADRE 2	459	126	SUBTOTAL QUADRE 3	213	187
NIQUADRE	PUNTS DE LLUM	LUMINÀRIES	POTENCIA (w)	POT. PROP (w)	PRESSUPOST																																																																										
Total 1	87	87	4802	2357	27.300,00 €																																																																										
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Total 7	117	117	12250	4600	35.100,00 €																																																																										
Total 8	4	8	340	140	2.400,00 €																																																																										
Total 9	4	4	600	160	2.400,00 €																																																																										
Total general substitució luminàries	491	516	69893	25787	170.480,00 €																																																																										
QUADRE	Importa TP (en k€) (K)	Nov Import TP																																																																													
SUBTOTAL QUADRE 1	347	102																																																																													
SUBTOTAL QUADRE 2	459	126																																																																													
SUBTOTAL QUADRE 3	213	187																																																																													
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Replacement of lighting with LED technology in the municipality of Aiguaviva																																																																														
Funding Programme: (If applicable)																																																																															
Project website: (If applicable)																																																																															
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.																																																																															
LLUMINÀRIES OBSOLETES	LLUMINÀRIES EFICIENTS																																																																														
Progress status - Start date:	02/2018																																																																														
End date:	07/2020																																																																														
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.																																																																															
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	By replacement of the existing lighting to LED technology the municipality of Aiguaviva can reach a reduction in energy consumption and a reduction in CO2 emissions. Also get saving form the electrici bills.																																																																														

Table 4-28. Local Energy Communities

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Local Energy Communities in Girona Province
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Renewable energy
	Energy communities
	Energy transition planning
Country:	Spain
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Municipalities of Girona Region (Spain)
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	Photovoltaic Local Energy Communities
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	8 municipalities with active communities with 391 connected residents
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	5 municipalities pending commissioning (installation executed)
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	37 municipalities in the execution phase
	33 municipalities in the planning phase
	25 pending planning
Project full title / acronym:	Local Energy Communities
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	2021
End date:	2023
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	By constituting 130 local energy communities 2860 houses will connect to a photovoltaic installation to reach energy savings
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	

Table 4-29. Electric car sharing service by Som Mobilitat in the municipality of Sant Joan les Abadesses.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Electric car sharing service by Som Mobilitat in the Municipality of Sant Joan les Abadesses.
Keywords:	Energy transition planning Energy communities
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	
Country:	Spain
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Sant Joan les Abadesses (Spain)
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Electric car sharing service by Som Mobilitat in the municipality of Sant Joan les Abadesses
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	<p>Our first offered service consists of a rental service of electric cars (car-sharing). These cars can be either owned by the cooperative or by individuals, enterprises and public institutions (p2p). Vehicles can be used by means of accessing a digital platform (using a web-app) that allows you to make reservations, open and close the vehicle. In addition, we are working to incorporate new sustainable mobility services to the platform, such as bike-sharing, motorbike-sharing or car-pooling and ride-sharing. And our future aim is set on the autonomous vehicle as shared resource.</p> <p>As we already know, the challenges posed by current mobility take place at the local level but have global responses. For this reason, Som Mobilitat is organized in the territory in local groups to ensure that it is the people of each municipality who promote and adapt the mobility services that we are creating in the realities of each neighborhood, town or city.</p> <p>At the same time, we are working on a network at European level to share good practices and resources with other sustainable mobility cooperatives to collaboratively face the global challenges of mobility and at the same time to build a social model that is an successful alternative to profit-oriented, private and vertical mobility proposals that are being implemented throughout Europe. In order to do so, we have created the first network of mobility cooperatives in Europe called REScoop Mobility, under the umbrella of the REScoop.eu cooperative federation.</p>
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Electric car sharing service by Som Mobilitat in the municipality of Sant Joan les Abadesses
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	
Project website: (If applicable)	
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	01/2023
End date:	
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies</i>	With this Electric car sharing service all citizens can have a new mobility way in rural areas with few public transport lines

Table 4-30. Biomass heat network for heating and DHW, in Ribes de Freser (Girona).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Biomass heat network for heating and DHW, in Ribes de Freser (Girona).
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures Energy Efficiency in buildings Methodology / tool / solution Energy transition planning
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Spain
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Ribes de Freser (Spain)
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Biomass heat network for heating and DHW, in Ribes de Freser (Girona)
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	Ribes de Freser is a municipality in the Ripollès region (Girona), with a fixed population of 1,900 people located in a high mountain environment and with a special sensitivity for the natural environment and the management of its forests. In 2011, the Ribes de Freser City Council put out to tender an Energy Services competition that included the design, construction and operation of a biomass heat network for public facilities. The contract is for energy supply with conduction and full guarantee of the facilities for a period of 20 years In 2014 and in accordance with what the contract made possible, an expansion of the network was carried out to connect private users, in this case Hotels. This expansion came into operation in October 2014 (Phase2).
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Biomass heat network for heating and DHW, in Ribes de Freser (Girona)
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	<p>EQUIPOS Caldera 1: 500 kW Caldera 2: 250 kW Depósitos de inercia: 3 x 5.000 l Bomba 1 red: 2,20 kW + CF Bomba 2 red: 5,50 kW + CF Bomba 3 red: 7,50 kW + CF Cuadro de control Depósito de agua expansión</p>
Progress status - Start date:	2012
End date:	2022
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	By executing this district heating, 6 Municipality buildings have renewable energy at Phase 1 and 4 hotels at Phase 2.

Table 4-31. Zagreb's smart energy solutions for citizens.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Zagreb's smart energy solutions for citizens.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Renewable energy
Country:	Croatia
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	North-West Croatia
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Developing energy-related digital tools for citizens: a Solar PV Potential tool, the Zagreb Energy Atlas and a Public Building Renovation Monitor.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	In 2022, the City of Zagreb together with REGEA (the North-West Croatia Regional Energy Agency) developed numerous energy-related digital tools aimed at citizens, including: 1. A Solar PV Potential tool, which enables the calculation of relevant parameters for installation of PV systems on buildings; The tool provides all relevant data for a preliminary feasibility estimation. Every residential building (both multi-apartment and family houses) located within the City of Zagreb can be selected directly by clicking on the city map or by searching its address. 2. The Zagreb Energy Atlas, which includes data on energy consumption for all buildings (public, residential, commercial) in the City of Zagreb and affords citizens the visualisation and analysis of aggregated data; 3. A Public Building Renovation Monitor, which presents relevant data and photo documentation regarding the renovation of public buildings in the City of Zagreb.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://fedarene.org/best-practice/zagrebs-smart-energy-solutions-for-citizens/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	June 2021
End date:	June 2024
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	The Solar PV Potential tool allows citizens to calculate PV parameters in case of the replacement of natural gas with electricity as a source of heating. The tool also automatically generates the documentation necessary to obtain the permits necessary for the PV installation from the electricity distribution company, which considerably speeds up the process and reduces preparation costs for citizens.

Table 4-32. One of Slovenia's first smart grid systems in a public building.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	One of Slovenia's first smart grid systems in a public building.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures Energy Efficiency in buildings Renewable energy
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Slovenia
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Destriuk
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	The Local Energy Agency Spodnje Podravje (LEASP) created a new smart grid for the kindergarten of Destriuk
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	Local Energy Agency Spodnje Podravje (LEASP) completed the DEMO project, a new smart grid for the Destriuk kindergarten. The applied technology consisted of: PV plant – 24 kWp; BYD battery premium 20 kWh (2 units); Solar edge hybrid inverter 10 kW (2 units); Battery control system – Solar edge, Schneider Ev Parking 2x22 kW T2 RFID with protective equipment, EV link LMS 5 for dynamic charging control, BMS controller Schneider ASB24 with web Scada; Schneider power-meter. The monitoring system controls the whole system and measures the electricity produced, consumed, charged, and released into the grid. The average electrical consumption of the kindergarten is 65.8 MWh/a. The planned production from PV is 26.4 MWh/a. After starting up the system, a hidden consumer of electricity was found to be draining 8.76 MWh/a before becoming eliminated. The total savings were estimated at 35.16 kWh/a or €8,320 per year. The payback period (including total investment of €71,890) is 8.6 years.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	DEMO project
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Interreg-Danube
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	<p>The diagram shows a micro-grid system with components: MPPPT, Stationary Batteries (48V), Charger Inverter, Inverter, Charger, and Electronic load/DSM. It also shows a screenshot of a monitoring dashboard with a bar chart of energy production and consumption, and a table of environmental benefits.</p> <p>Figure 1. The micro-grid under study, comprising a photovoltaic system with storage, an electric vehicle, and a Demand-Side-Management (DSM) system represented by a programmable electronic load. In the middle, a relay board controls R1, R2, and R3.</p>
Progress status - Start date:	2019
End date:	2023
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	The main benefit besides energy savings is strong demonstration impact and the great interest of the other municipalities now seeking to implement similar projects. In addition, from the start-up of the system, 4.8t of CO2 emissions were saved.

Table 4-33. SIE - the energy management software.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	SIE - the energy management software.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution Energy Efficiency in buildings
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	
Country:	Spain
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	More than 500 city councils throughout Spain.
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	A comprehensive solution to reduce the electric bill, energy consumption, and CO2 emissions of the municipal buildings.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	The Energy Management Software is a comprehensive solution for municipalities to manage the supplies of all municipal buildings. The tool enables monitoring of energy consumption, whatever its origin, and water consumption. It is prepared to gather data from many different sources, such as billing, Distribution System Operator API, and web from trading companies. In most cases, these gathering capabilities automatize the data acquisition procedure, leading to increased implementation speed. Moreover, as the same information can be obtained from different agents, the billing and accounting of the different supplies can be validated. Indeed, taking advantage of the collected data, the software can proportionate several services to control energy consumption and reduce costs. These services are from optimization of the contracted power capacity or consumption analysis to over-consumption alarms.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	SIE (Energy Information System)
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://www.inergybcn.com/en/sie/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	1/2012
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Municipalities have a software of reference which enables them to track and manage efficiently their energy supplies.
References:	https://www.inergybcn.com/en/sie/

Table 4-34. Solar energy potential of buildings in Spain.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Solar energy potential of buildings in Spain.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution Renewable energy
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	
Country:	Spain
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	The web viewer allows you to enter any location and displays the PV capacity of the building's roof and a mesh of points to locate the best site.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	The web viewer allows you to enter any location in the Spanish territory and displays the PV capacity of the building's rooftops and a mesh of points to locate the best site. The data used for the processing comes from buildings of the General Directorate of Cadastre, the Government of Navarre, the Basque Government, the 2-metre digital surface model of the National Geographic Institute obtained from LiDAR data and the European Commission. The design of the tool involves the creation of two standard web services WMS and WMTS to show the solar potential. Such tools allow installation companies and public and private users to estimate the solar potential prior to installation. They also help to determine the best location for the panels.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	Spanish Government, PERTE (Proyectos Estratégicos para la Recuperación y Transformación Económica)
Project website: (If applicable)	https://eficiencia-energetica.ign.es/solar
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	11/2023
End date:	-
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	A new version of the web visualiser with extended functionalities such as installation cost simulators depending on the type of panels, annual solar potential curve or 3D visualiser.
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	Solar potential of any roof in Spain. Best location on the roof.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described	Spanish Geographical National Institut Thematic viewer: https://www.ign.es/web/ign/portal/visualizadores-tematicos

Table 4-35. Energy community planning tool: Som Comunitat Energètica

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Energy community planning tool: Som Comunitat Energètica
Keywords:	Energy communities
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Renewable energy
Country:	Spain
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Catalonia
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Tool to help citizens plan energy communities and organise themselves or with the help of a technician.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	The approach of the project is to build a knowledge base for the entire Catalan territory, from the metropolitan areas to the micro-towns, which allows the exposure to the potential of creating energy communities and the advantages they bring in the social spheres -more cohesion and empowerment, economic -less energy cost, and environmental -consumption reduction and decarbonisation. Aware of the danger of the transition occurring based on inequality, the differential premise is the inclusion of the entire built fabric of towns and cities to avoid, once again, being left out of the process the most vulnerable sectors.
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	The online platform SomComunitatEnergetica.cat is the resulting tool that will make accessible all the knowledge generated and that will facilitate communication between the key agents in the energy transition. It provides, in an agile and intuitive way, the essential and appropriate indicators for the administration, market entities, companies and neighbouring communities, with an eye on public planning, the implementation of large-scale projects and citizen empowerment.
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Som Comunitat Energètica
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Government funding
Project website:	https://somcomunitatenergetica.cat/

<p><i>(if applicable)</i></p> <p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>01/2021</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>06/2022</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>The main outcome of the project is the online platform. The online platform allows citizens to create a user to plan an energy community. To help in the process, the platform has tools and relevant information to estimate the users' energy consumption. Moreover, it has the estimation of rooftop PV production capability from all the residential buildings of Catalonia. With this tool, the users can estimate all the energy community consumption and its generation capabilities.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i></p>	<p>https://info.somcomunitatenergetica.cat/</p>

Table 4-36. Generating resilient actions against the heat island effect on urban territory.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Generating resilient actions against the heat island effect on urban territory.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	
Country:	France
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Toulouse
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Create a new green lung in the city of Toulouse, and to study the effects of revegetation in cities with the objective of mitigating the urban heat island effect.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]	In response to the changing climate, particularly the urban heat island (UHI) effect that amplifies increasingly frequent heat waves, the LIFE Green Heart project aims to increase the resilience of the Toulouse Metropol. Specifically, the project's main objective is to reduce the local temperature by 3C on average during heatwave events on an area of 30 hectares on the Ile du Ramier in Toulouse by counteracting the UHI effect. The project includes four operational objectives to address the causes and consequences of the UHI effect: 1) Increasing green space surface area using adapted plants and planting methods 2) Restoring biodiversity by consolidating green and blue infrastructure 3) Reducing air and noise pollution by developing routes for soft modes of transport (e.g. bicycle lanes) 4) Creating tools to support the development of long-term urban development policy, considering climate change adaptation
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Generate RESiliENT actions agaiNst the HEat islanD effect on uRban Territory / LIFE Green Heart
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	LIFE programme
Project website: (If applicable)	
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	09/2019
End date:	09/2024
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	This project proportionates experience in dealing with climate adaptation measures. This study could also point to the direction in which the cities could adapt to heat waves, reducing its effect and improving the quality of life for its citizens.
References:	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE18-CCA-FR-001150/generate-resilient-actions-against-the-heat-island-effect-on-urban-territory

Table 4-37. Energy Efficiency in public lighting in the Municipality of Baião.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS
TITLE:	Energy Efficiency in public lighting in the Municipality of Baião.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition planning Public lighting Methodology / tool / solution Governance structure Energy transition measures
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Portugal
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Municipality of Baião, District of Porto, Country Portugal
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Replacement of all public lighting in the entire territory of the municipality of Baião, with LED technology lighting.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Technical solutions [e.g. innovative technical tools/methodologies/solutions developed to increase energy-efficiency in public buildings or sustainable mobility; case studies of successful implementation of such solutions in actual projects; etc.]</i>	In order to continue the work previously carried out, in the POVT (Operational Territory Valorization Program) where the project "Energy Efficiency in Public Lighting in the Municipality of Baião - 1st phase" was implemented, the municipality submitted an application to PO-Norte 2020, with the aim of implementing the 2nd phase of replacing existing traditional luminaires with LED technology luminaires, in order to promote greater and better energy efficiency in the municipality of Baião, contributing to a reduction in energy consumption and a consequent reduction in CO2 emissions . The Ex-Ante diagnosis/study was carried out, which resulted in the implementation project. The project stipulated the need to replace 7,452 LED luminaires, with power equal to 28W, 38W, 53W, 55W and 80W. The value of the service was 1213 thousand euros, with financing of 770 thousand euros from PO-Norte2020 under a reimbursable subsidy. For the remaining investment, the Municipality of Baião resorted to financing from the European Investment Bank.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Energy Efficiency in public lighting in the Municipality of Baião
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Programa Operacional Regional do Norte – Norte 2020 (PO - Norte2020)
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Not applicable
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	15/03/2018
End date:	02/07/2021
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Annual bill for public lighting - Baião 2019 - 434 624,00€ 2020 - 374 817,54€ 2021 - 181 991,41€ 2022 - 202 06,75€ There is a reduction in the annual bill from 2019 to 2022. However, these values are also related to the variation in the price of energy, as well as the values of fees, tariffs and taxes associated with electricity supply bills.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports/photos/videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	https://www.cm-baiiao.pt/2020/10/06/camara-de-baiiao-substitui-toda-a-iluminacao-publica-do-concelho-por-lampadas-led/ https://amarantemagazine.sapo.pt/sociedade/baiiao-camara-coloca-lampadas-led-em-todo-o-concelho/ https://www.marcoensefm.com/noticias/baiiao-municipio-aposta-na-substituicao-de-luminarias/

5 Best Practices and Solutions in Financing

This chapter includes existing innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition and case studies of the successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects.

Table 5-1. Leading role of the Zlin Region in developing low-carbon districts within the Czech Republic.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Leading role of the Zlin Region in developing low-carbon districts within the Czech Republic.
Keywords:	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Methodology / tool / solution
	EU funding
	Energy transition measures
	Public authorities' cooperation
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	Spain, Croatia, Italy, Sweden, Czech Republic
Region / Municipality / location:	Regions of Navarra (Spain), Marche (Italy), Smaland (Sweden), Zlin Region (Czech Republic), North West (Croatia)
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description:	International project LC DISTRICTS has brought a significant impact in improvement of regional development policies and programmes in the areas of building renovation and construction of energy efficient buildings, creation and renovation of district heating and other urban renovation actions, in order to facilitate the transition to low-carbon districts and municipalities.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	As for the Czech side within the projects, LC DISTRICTS created a unique opportunity to connect the regional and national level through the cooperation of EAZK with institutions at the national level – Czech Technical University, State Environmental Fund or Ministry of the Environment.
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].	Also, participation in the LC DISTRICTS project enabled both EAZK and the Zlin Region itself not only to capitalize on its experience but also to be inspired by examples from partner regions in Navarre (ESP), Småland (SWE), Ancona (IT) and Croatia, and to utilise all existing and new knowledge to engage into the process of determining the form of OP Environment Czech Rep. for the following programming period 2021 – 2027.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subsidy support from OPE as part of the modernization of public buildings was increased for comprehensive measures and achieving maximum energy savings, - The supported measures were expanded, and the administrative complexity of the projects was reduced. - Subsidy support from OPE for the construction of new buildings was increased from the existing 30 to 32% and a maximum limit of CZK 50 million to 50% and a maximum limit of CZK 120 million for passive buildings and 70% and a maximum limit of CZK 140 million for active buildings . - The transfer of experience with the construction of passive buildings was successfully imported into other subsidy programs, e.g. IROP (Integrated regional operational program) - The use of functional examples from other countries in terms of ambitions, used materials and a comprehensive approach was an inspiration for the key subjects forming the final form of the national operational programs.
Project full title / acronym:	Towards Low Carbon City Districts Through The Improvement Of Regional Policies (LC DISTRICTS)
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.	
Funding Programme:	Interreg Europe
(If applicable)	
Project website:	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/lcdistricts/
(If applicable)	
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	
Progress status - Start date:	08/2019
End date:	01/2023
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Thanks to the comprehensive concept of the LC DISTRICTS project and the action plan created for the Zlin Region within the project, EAZK will not only play the role of facilitator for municipalities and regions through the submission of targeted and carefully selected projects but will also play an important role in providing feedback at the national level for further adaptations of the program for its most efficient use for the benefit of the end users.
Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	
References:	(1) INTERREG EUROPE
Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/lcdistricts/
	(2) FEDARENE
	https://fedarene.org/best-practice/leading-role-of-the-zlin-region-in-developing-low-carbon-districts-within-the-czech-republic/

Table 5-2. ESCOLIMBURG2020

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	ESCOLIMBURG2020
Keywords:	Energy transition planning
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Innovative financing
Country:	Belgium
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Province of Limbrug Infrac Dubolimborg
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	The project translates provincial and municipal climate ambitions into practice: by focusing on making the existing heritage of municipal and provincial buildings more energy-efficient more quickly.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	The ESCOLIMBURG2020 project translates provincial and municipal climate ambitions into practice: by focusing on making the existing heritage of municipal and provincial buildings more energy-efficient (energy renovation and renewable energy) more quickly. The existing ESCO of the provincial energy grid operator Infrac will serve as a starting point for this. For the municipalities, it is important that they set the right example in the context of their local climate policy: practice what you preach. ESCO takes an integrated approach and approaches the building as a total concept. Our starting point is the Total Cost of Ownership and we always propose the most optimal solution, while taking into account payback periods, available budgets and of course, the requirements and needs of the administration and the people on the work floor. We are ALWAYS looking for the best possible solution. ESCO offered its extensive know-how and experience to a thorough and total renovation of the building, with opportunities for towns to prepare their heritage for the future in a financially efficient manner. ESCO provided the perfect way to implement the obligations arising out of the signing of the Covenant Of Mayors. ESCO offered new financing possibilities and techniques that fit within the new BBC.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	
Project full title / acronym:	ESCOLIMBURG2020
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	Intelligent Energy Europe Funding programme
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://www.escolimborg2020.be/en/esco
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	April 2013
End date:	March 2017
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	https://www.escolimborg2020.be/en/downloads
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	

Table 5-3. *Rénov'Occitanie: One-Stop-Shops for Energy Renovations and Savings in Occitanie.*

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Rénov'Occitanie: One-Stop-Shops for Energy Renovations and Savings in Occitanie.
Keywords:	Energy Efficiency in buildings
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	EU funding
	Innovative financing
	Energy transition measures
Country:	France
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Occitanie
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	Rénov'Occitanie is a public service for renovations of private housing led by the Occitanie Region since January 2021. It provides a complete support for citizens of Occitanie to carry out energy renovation work, rely on renewable energy and reduce energy bills.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	This service includes, among other things, an offer of a subsidised loan carried by AREC and aims to facilitate the financing of the remaining costs of the operations beyond public aid.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote quality work and adapted financing plans Improve winter and summer comfort To aim for a balanced budget Enhance the value of the heritage. <p>Deployment of the activity</p> <p>The Rénov'Occitanie activity is being deployed to offer citizens of the region service to accompany them in energy renovation projects for their homes with a 2-step process:</p> <p>Definition of the home improvement project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy audit Delivery of a report with at least two work scenarios (-40% and BBC Renovation) Establishment of a financing plan. Accompanying the work Analysis of estimates Assistance in writing applications for grants Assistance to the project owner for the follow-up and acceptance of the work (2 visits) Consumption monitoring
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	From 2021
End date:	
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	Based on local public and private cooperation, 31 one-stop-shops spread across the territory are available for a primary contact. As neutral, objective, impartial and independent places, they provide free information and advice on energy related issues at home (rational use of energy, energy efficiency, renewable energy etc.)
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	
References:	
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	

Table 5-4. Scaling up the energy refurbishment of public buildings in small and mid-size local authorities.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Scaling up the energy refurbishment of public buildings in small and mid-size local authorities.
Keywords: <i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures EU funding Innovative financing
Country: <i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	France
Region / Municipality / location: <i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Auvergne Rhône-Alpes region.
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	BAPAURA is a three-year project which aims at facilitating the refurbishment of public buildings in small and mid-size municipalities which often overlook the energy efficiency portion of their works as a result of the proportionally high costs of setting-up such projects. This project is fully funded by the European program for research and innovation Horizon 2020 (total budget: €1.475.594.)
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	Two levels of action: A set of tools put together. A toolbox will be built step by step and will be made available for the support service structures. A first meeting took place on 8th December 2020 in order to level the ground of the shared knowledge and identify the needs of the project partners. An energy renovation support service by the territorial partners. They will provide, share and build on their energy performance and financial engineering expertise with the aim to see through the project's energy refurbishment projects and help others do likewise. A regional facilitation carried by ADEME and AURA-EE to align the objectives of the regional toolbox with the National and European standards and ambitions.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	BAPAURA
Funding Programme: <i>(if applicable)</i>	
Project website: <i>(if applicable)</i>	

<p>Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.</p>	<p>9 experimental territories: partners with a diverse background for a targeted support of each territory.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agence locale de la transition énergétique du Rhône • Agence locale de l'énergie et du climat de l'Ain • SPL ALEC de la Grande région grenobloise • Communauté de communes Châtaigneraie cantalienne • Syndicat départemental d'énergie de l'Allier • Syndicat de gestion des énergies de la région lyonnaise • Syndicat départemental d'énergies de la Drôme • Association pour une gestion durable de l'énergie • SARA AMENAGEMENT - Groupe ELEGIA
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>2021</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>2023</p>
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</p>	<p>Energy Efficiency Investments in Public Buildings: Facilitating energy efficiency investments in 115 public buildings, resulting in a total investment of EUR 23.6 million, leading to reduced energy consumption and operational costs in these facilities.</p> <p>Centralized Energy Services for Small and Mid-Size Municipalities: Establishing advanced and centralized energy services tailored to the specific needs of small and mid-size municipalities, offering comprehensive project development assistance encompassing legal, technical, and financial support.</p> <p>Streamlined Department-Level Services: Ensuring easy access to these energy services at the departmental level through the integration of "one-stop shop" services within nine existing local energy support structures, simplifying the process for municipalities.</p> <p>Local Mobilization of Stakeholders: Mobilizing local service providers, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and financial institutions to actively participate in energy efficiency projects, creating a collaborative ecosystem for sustainable initiatives.</p> <p>Innovative Financing Solutions: Introducing innovative financing models by optimizing municipalities' investment plans, exploring diverse financing options, adapting grant schemes, standardizing subsidy applications, and leveraging white certificates to make energy efficiency projects financially viable and attractive.</p> <p>Scalable Replication: Developing a toolkit over the project's duration that allows for the replication of successful project outcomes at regional and national levels, promoting wider adoption of energy efficiency practices and investments across the country.</p> <p>Regenerate</p>
<p>References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</p>	<p>https://en.auvergne-rhone-alpes-ee.fr/fileadmin/user_upload/mediatheque/raee/Images/Projets_europeens/BAPAUURA_newsletter_February_2021.pdf</p>

Table 5-5. Sun4All financial support scheme for renewable energy access.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Sun4All financial support scheme for renewable energy access.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Renewable energy
	Energy communities
	Innovative financing
	Public authorities' cooperation
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	France, Italy, Portugal, Spain
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Municipality of Almada (Portugal), Municipality of Barcelona (Spain), Communauté de Communes Coeur de Savoie (France), Municipality of Rome (Italy)
Short description:	Sun4All financial support scheme for renewable energy access for energy vulnerable households. The scheme offers vulnerable consumers the opportunity to subscribe to community solar.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	<u>Methodology:</u> The Sun4All project aims at facilitating access to renewable energy generation (and its economic and environmental benefits) for vulnerable households, which suffer from energy poverty, and which otherwise would not have the capacity of investing in solar installations. The Sun4All project sets-up a financial support scheme that is already running with success in the United States of America. The existing New York State initiative – utility bill assistance programme named “Solar for All” is now adopted into the European context.
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Eurosolar for all: energy communities for a fair energy transition in Europe /SUN4All
Funding Programme:	European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://sunforall.eu/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	

<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	<p>Get to know the Sun4All support scheme</p> <p>Solar energy is generated by local photovoltaic installations owned by the municipality and located near to where eligible participants live.</p> <p>Depending on the pilot site, some the renewable solar energy is either provided for direct consumption by eligible beneficiaries or fed into the local power grid.</p> <p>Sun4All beneficiaries participate in getting electricity for small, with no need to install, or installed solar panels.</p> <p>Through the financial support scheme and by redistributive mechanisms, Sun4All participants financially benefit from the renewable energy produced and its value.</p>
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>10/2021</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>09/2024 (Ongoing)</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>The Sun4All project financial support scheme has been adapted to the contextual characteristics of each of the pilot locations, ensuring that all implemented activities are local needs oriented. One of the objectives of the project is to be sustainable and replicable throughout Europe. To ensure that Sun4All is sustainable and replicable throughout Europe, a Community of Practice of the European cities was established to follow the project and plan a replication of the Sun4All schemes in their regions. The Community of Practice observes the pilots' implementation to get some first-hand experience and work more effectively on their own specific energy poverty eradication plans and local business models.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i></p>	<p>(1) Blueprint model for the Sun4All model (ENG): https://sunforall.eu/resource?t=Blueprint%20model%20for%20the%20Sun4All%20programme</p> <p>(2) The EU framework on energy communities (ENG): https://sunforall.eu/resource?t=The%20EU%20framework%20on%20energy%20communities</p> <p>(3) Sun4All Capacity and Training Package (ENG): https://sunforall.eu/resource?t=Sun4All%20Capacity%20and%20Training%20Package</p>

Table 5-6. Solutions Gateway Finance decision-making support tool.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Solutions Gateway Finance decision-making support tool.
Keywords:	Innovative financing
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Methodology / tool / solution
	Renewable energy
	Energy transition measures
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Austria; Belgium; Bulgaria; Denmark; Finland; France; Germany; Hungary; Iceland; Netherlands; Portugal; Romania; Spain; Sweden; Turkey; United Kingdom
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Almada, Portugal; Amsterdam, Netherlands; Barcelona, Spain; Burgas, Bulgaria; Cambourne, United Kingdom; Cascais, Portugal; Copenhagen, Denmark; Dundee, United Kingdom; Gipuzkoa, Spain; Hamburg, Germany; Helsinki, Finland; Istanbul, Turkey; Köln, Germany; Lille Metropole, France; Linköping, Sweden; Lund, Sweden; Malmö, Sweden; Milton Keynes, United Kingdom; Miskolc, Hungary; Oss, Netherlands; Paris, France; Porto, Portugal; Reykjavik, Iceland; Southampton, United Kingdom; Tirgu Mures, Romania; Tomar, Portugal; Turnhout, Belgium; Vienna, Austria; Weiz, Austria; Zaragoza, Spain
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	Solution Gateway's Finance Facilitation Tool helps local governments identify financing options to implement projects / realize their Low Emission Development Strategies.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	Solutions Gateway is an online resource platform for local and regional governments to find relevant Low Emissions Development (LED) solutions and support. It provides access to a wide range of tools and resources, including a Finance Facilitation Tool to help policymakers to identify and access relevant financial resources to support their LED projects. The platform contains sectoral and cross-sectoral packages of activities, structured along local government responsibilities and spheres of influence, to support cities in the development of low-emission strategies, plans, and projects. The Solutions Gateway contents are based on proven technologies and practices, distilled into "Solutions" and "Solution Packages" related to Sustainable Urban Transport; Energy Efficiency; Renewable Energy; and Climate Change Adaptation Actions which are drafted and peer-reviewed by experts of the respective field. The Solutions Gateway Finance decision-making support tool operates as a decision tree, systematically directing local and regional government entities. It achieves this by presenting a sequence of binary questions (yes or no) to facilitate the assessment of potential financing mechanisms for specific projects or to support the funding of those projects.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Solutions Gateway Finance decision-making support tool
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Solutions Gateway was developed under the Urban-LEDS project, funded by the European Union, and jointly implemented by IICLEI and UN-Habitat.
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://www.solutions-gateway.org/show?page=financetool

<p>Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.</p>	<p>The image shows the logos for 'solutionsgateway Climate, Energy, and Finance Solutions' and 'URBAN LEDS URBAN LOW EMISSION DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES'. Below the logos is a diagram titled 'CLIMATE FINANCE DECISION MAKING TREE' which is a flowchart showing various financing instruments and their associated benefits and drawbacks.</p>
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>07/2012</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>03/2015</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	<p>The dates above refer to the tool's development period. In 2016, it was only available to the cities that were part of the Urban-Leds project and since then it has become a freely accessible platform that remains active.</p>
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>The climate finance decision-making tree provides a structured path for local and regional governments, leading them through a series of inquiries aimed at facilitating the exploration of various financing instruments. Each financing tool is comprehensively outlined, encompassing its benefits, drawbacks, and illustrated with relevant case study instances. An overview of the decision-making tree and the financing tools available to local and regional governments is provided at (1) https://urban-leds.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Finance-tree_EN_final-min.pdf; in English or at https://urban-leds.org/resource-library/guidance-tools/#climate-finance; in Spanish, Portuguese, French and Chinese.</p> <p>Examples of cities who used the Finance Facilitation Tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nagpur, India used the tool to identify and access funding for its \$1.3 billion Smart City project, which includes a range of LED initiatives, such as the development of a bus rapid transit system and the installation of energy-efficient LED streetlights. - Freiburg, Germany used the tool to find funding for its Green City Project, which has helped the city to become one of the most sustainable in Germany. The project includes a range of LED initiatives, such as the development of a district heating system and the promotion of cycling and walking. - Melbourne, Australia used the tool to identify and access funding for its Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, which includes a range of measures to help the city adapt to the impacts of climate change, such as sea level rise and extreme heat events. - Oslo, Norway used the tool to find funding for its Oslo 2030 Strategy, which aims to make Oslo a zero-carbon city by 2030. The strategy includes a range of LED initiatives, such as the development of renewable energy sources and the promotion of electric vehicles.
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i></p>	<p>(1) Climate finance decision making tree (ENG) https://urban-leds.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Finance-tree_EN_final-min.pdf</p> <p>(2) Climate finance glossary (ENG) https://urban-leds.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Climate-finance-glossary.pdf</p> <p>(3) Solutions Gateway Sourcebook - Easy-to-use guidance for local governments: Low Carbon Solutions for Urban Development Challenges (ENG) https://e-lib.iclel.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/ICLEI_Solutions-Gateway-Sourcebook_final-web1.pdf</p> <p>(4) Session 1: Solutions Gateway and Pool of Experts Webinar (ENG) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AO2lpVqMCuQ</p> <p>(5) Session 2: Solutions Gateway and Pool of Experts Webinar (ENG) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JKSTVGkLuTc</p>

Table 5-7. Integrated Sustainable Energy Actions and projects in Crete, funded through ELENA.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND STRUCTURES
TITLE:	Integrated Sustainable Energy Actions and projects in Crete, funded through ELENA.
Keywords:	Multi-level governance
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Renewable energy
	Governance structure
	Public lighting
	Energy communities
Country:	Greece
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	REGION OF CRETE
Short description:	3 pillars for energy transition: 1) energy upgrade of street lighting 2) energy performance of hospitals and health centers 3) establishment of energy communities to build PV parks.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	The investments related to street lighting and public buildings are planned to be implemented through EPC/ESCO or PPP schemes where private capital is used to co-fund public infrastructure projects. It is also planned to blend these funding with European Structural and Investment Funds and with State Funding in order to finance works for which the pay-back is not attractive enough to be included in the EPC contracts.
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	The integrated Renewable Energy investments will be implemented through the set-up of at least 4 Energy Communities. The PV panels will be used for self-consumption of the buildings and the set-up will provide the possibility of Virtual Net-metering in order to spread the benefits to more than one facility of each Land Reclamation Local Authorities concerned. The Investment Programme consists of 3 schemes addressing energy efficiency measures in the regional and municipal street lighting network (approx. 38,000 lighting points), implementation of Energy Efficiency Retrofits in Public Buildings (over 200,000 sqm in 16 hospitals and health centres and administration buildings belonging to the Crete Region) and the installation of 68,000 sqm of solar PV integrated to buildings belonging to municipalities and public organizations, through the set-up of Energy Communities.
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	INTEgrated sustainable enERgy ACTIONs and projects in Crete (INTERACT in Crete)
Funding Programme:	ELENA – European Local ENergy Assistance
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://interactincrete.eu/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	

<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	<p>The image shows three logos: 'INTERACT in Crete' with the tagline 'Energy Saving Made..', the 'European Investment Bank' logo with the tagline 'The EIB bank', and the 'REGION OF CRETE' logo with the Greek text 'ΠΕΡΙΦΕΡΕΙΑ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ'.</p>
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>12/2020</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>Ongoing (expected end date Q4 2023)</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>The total estimated contributions are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Efficiency – Annual total energy saved 25.1 GWh representing a reduction of 41% compared to the baseline. • Renewable Energy – Annual total 17.7 GWh, of which: 7.3 GWh RE heat and 10.4 GWh RE electricity generation • CO2 reductions – Annual total reductions of 26 900 CO2 eq t representing a reduction of 63% compared to the baseline. • Jobs retained or created - 263 equivalent FTE
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i></p>	<p>https://www.eib.org/attachments/documents/119-project-factsheet-interact-in-</p>

Table 5-8. Helping consumers in Castilla y León face the effects of the energy crisis.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Helping consumers in Castilla y León face the effects of the energy crisis.
Keywords:	EU funding
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Country:	Spain
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Castilla y León Region
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	EREN launched 2 subsidy programmes supported by over €80M from NextGenerationEU funds. They fund self-consumption and renewable energy storage projects, as well as thermal energy upgrades in buildings across the region.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	Through actions developed by EREN, the Regional Energy Agency of Castilla y León, consumers are responding to the international energy crisis. They launched 2 subsidy programmes supported by over €80M from NextGenerationEU funds and funding self-consumption and renewable energy storage projects, as well as thermal energy upgrades in buildings across the region. To reduce fossil fuel dependence, priority is given to works and actions for the improvement of energy efficiency in buildings owned by the regional administration.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].</i>	On a quarterly basis, a monitoring report shall be submitted to the Regional Government, drawn up by EREN, which shall contain a quantification of the consumption of electricity and gas and a comparison with the consumption recorded in the same period of the previous year. EREN is responsible for providing technical assistance to the different bodies of the administration within the scope of its powers.
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	NextGenerationEU fund
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://fedarene.org/best-practice/eren-helping-consumers-in-castilla-y-leon-face-the-effects-of-the-energy-crisis/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	

<p>Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.</p>	
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>January 2022</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>2023</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>Many new energy-saving and efficiency measures financed, development of an information campaign and energy-savings press and radio campaign.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i></p>	<p>https://energia.jcyl.es/web/es/energia-mineria-castilla-leon.html</p>

Table 5-9. Engaging citizens and local entities - the "Porto Energy Hub" one-stop-shop.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Engaging citizens and local entities – the "Porto Energy Hub" one-stop-shop.
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Governance structure
	Innovative financing
Country:	Portugal
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	Porto Metropolitan Area
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Supporting public and private entities in developing a bold renovation programme, mainstreaming new financial schemes in the Porto Metropolitan Area.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	The project focuses on existing family buildings, in particular social and low-income housing, both public and privately owned. Its principal goal is, by the end of the project, to have 3,000 refurbished dwellings and 12MW of PV installed capacity. PEER must also mobilise an investment of €27.2M in the renovation of energy-efficient housing and renewable energy in the region. The achievement of these objectives is well underway and has already benefitted from the close collaboration maintained between municipalities and housing entities. The collaboration will ultimately allow for the continuous improvement of the energy performance and living conditions of around 25,700 vulnerable households in the municipality.
Project full title / acronym:	Porto Energy Elevator (PEER)
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	H2020
Project website: (If applicable)	https://portoenergyhub.pt/

<p>Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i></p>	
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>June 2021</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>June 2024</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>One of the most visible outputs of the project is the creation of a one-stop-shop (OSS). The OSS fosters private investment and helps citizens to engage in energy efficiency and renewable energy production, as well as to gather the tools required to guide citizens throughout the whole renovation process.</p> <p>In addition, several financial incentives for citizens were developed to be implemented by municipalities, including the reduction of property taxes and framework agreements, which were designed to promote the private implementation of renewable energy production.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly</i></p>	<p>https://fedarene.org/best-practice/engaging-citizens-and-local-entities-the-porto-energy-hub-one-stop-shop/</p>

Table 5-10. Achieving carbon neutrality in Waterford Council (Ireland).

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	FINANCING MECHANISMS
TITLE:	Achieving carbon neutrality in Waterford Council (Ireland).
Keywords:	Public lighting
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Innovative financing
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Renewable energy
Country:	Ireland
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Waterford City and County
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	The council has invested in a €9 million project to replace around 15,000 public lights with energy-efficient LED lights, leading to significant energy savings.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters)	The council has invested in a €9 million project to replace around 15,000 public lights with energy-efficient LED lights, leading to significant energy savings. Additionally, the council aims to make all of its buildings carbon neutral by 2025 and has implemented various measures, such as upgrading building insulation, installing new heating systems, and developing solar PV projects. It is expected that work will commence later in 2022 and be complete by Qtr 2 2023. When implemented the project will lead to over 55% savings in energy use and GHG emissions arising from our public lights and will also provide much greater system reliability while reducing maintenance costs.
Describe a best practice in the field of Financing mechanisms [e.g. existing/ innovative financing mechanisms that could be used by public authorities to fund projects accelerating energy transition; case studies of successful deployment of such mechanisms in implemented projects].	
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/ national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Energy Efficient Public Lighting
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	National
Project website: (If applicable)	https://waterfordcouncil.ie/departments/environment/carbon-neutral-waterford/strategy.htm
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	https://waterfordcouncil.ie/images/carbon-neutral/PL%20LED%20lamp.jpg
Progress status - Start date:	Nov.2022
End date:	Ongoing
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	Energy savings. Energy-efficient LED lights.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is	https://waterfordcouncil.ie/departments/environment/carbon-neutral-waterford/strategy.htm

6 Best Practices and Solutions in Training activities

In this chapter, training and capacity building best practices are recorded. Learning communities, educational platforms, support toolkits as well as site visits from territories with less mature plans on energy transition to other more mature ones already implementing actions are included.

Table 6-1. openENTRANCE

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	openENTRANCE
Keywords:	Energy transition planning
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy transition measures
	Methodology / tool / solution
	EU funding
	Training seminars
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	openENTRANCE is developing, using and disseminating an open, transparent and integrated modelling platform for assessing low-carbon transition pathways in Europe
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]</i>	<p>The openENTRANCE (open EEnergy TRansition ANalyses for a low-Carbon Economy) developed and disseminated an open, transparent and integrated modelling platform for assessing low-carbon transition pathways in Europe.</p> <p>The openENTRANCE modelling platform shed light on the implications and economic costs associated to the different energy pathways that Europe could take towards its climate goals. With this scientific basis, openENTRANCE aims at helping social, economic and political actors in a better decision making. Allows carrying out scientific calculations and assessments for different future options of a low-carbon Europe. Links and integrates macro-economic and energy system models, and provides economic (e.g. GDP, employment) and human behavioural data (e.g. energy consumption habits) relevant for the energy transition to be used in modelling analyses. Supports stakeholders to determine macro-economic consequences of the energy transition and identify the best ways to transition to a 'low-carbon' economy. Is openly available to use by any interested users, targeting mainly researchers and modellers.</p>
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	openENTRANCE (open EEnergy TRansition ANalyses for a low-Carbon Economy)
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	Horizon 2020
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://openentrance.eu/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	May 2019
End date:	April 2023
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study</i>	

Table 6-2. EnergyCities: the European learning community for future-proof cities.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	EnergyCities
Keywords:	Energy communities
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Renewable energy
	Governance structure
	Multi-level governance
	Energy transition measures
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Europe
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	
Short description:	It is a community of several hundred local authority representatives from 30 countries. The network gathers frontrunners and energy transition beginners, city officials and technical experts, to empower cities to transition to future proof cities.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	Energy Cities is a learning community for cities engaged in future proofing their economies, built around a "local & sustainable first" approach. There are no conditions to join other than the ambition and the commitment to share experiences. The strength lies in the members' strong commitment to reach climate neutrality in their territories by 2050 and to align their local strategic development with the Paris Agreement.
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]</i>	Building a learning community is a tool that helps each of the members feel more confident in their own transition journey, because other cities have done it before, or because cities can test new solutions together. They foster an atmosphere of mutual trust in the dialogue between citizens, local leaders and EU & national institutions in order to accelerate the transformation towards a climate-neutral Europe. Energy Cities energises this vibrant community and ensures its visibility.
	The board of Directors is the political core group of the network.
Project full title / acronym:	EnergyCities: the European learning community for future-proof cities.
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	
Funding Programme:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Project website:	https://energy-cities.eu/
<i>(If applicable)</i>	
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	
End date:	ongoing
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	

Table 6-3. PROSPECT+: Capacity building for cities and regions - from learning to action!

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	PROSPECT+: Capacity building for cities and regions - from learning to action!
Keywords:	Training seminars
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Renewable energy
	EU funding
	Innovative financing
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	EU LEVEL
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description:	PROSPECT+ is a capacity-building H2020 project for cities and regions that follows and elaborates on the outcomes of the successfully completed project PROSPECT. The announcement of this project comes with great excitement to continue the support of EU cities and regions on their way to adopting energy efficiency practices and policies. PROSPECT+ focuses on 5 learning modules: 1. public buildings, 2. private buildings, 3. public lighting, 4. transport, and 5. cross-sectoral.
(Up to 150 characters)	
Long description:	PROSPECT+ is building on the results and success of the previous H2020 project – PROSPECT that enabled over 150 cities and regions to learn from their peers about innovative financing schemes and how implement sustainable energy projects. Now, the aim is to engage over 300 Public Authorities (PAs), and over 400 public officers. This will be accomplished through the Capacity Building Programme and additional replication activities.
(Up to 1000 characters)	
Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]	Cities are the main contributors to pollution and climate change, but they also have the power and opportunity to deliver the highest savings, provide a good example and drive the energy transition. Financing local authorities' sustainable energy and climate projects is hindered primarily by a lack of internal capacity to identify the most appropriate and cost-effective financing instruments and implementation models. In this respect, PROSPECT+ continues to support EU cities and regions on their way to successfully implement their local energy and climate actions using innovative financing. The Capacity- Building Programme aims to promote synergies and enhance city decision-making processes regarding the implementation of energy efficiency measures. The Capacity- Building Programme consists of five (5) thematic learning modules 1. Public Buildings, 2. Private Buildings, 3. Transport, 4. Public Lighting, 5. Cross Sectoral The learning process will follow a mixed approach combining physical meetings (Study visits and Local mentoring) and teleconferences/webinars.

<p>Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local/national initiative, a private initiative etc.</p> <p>Funding Programme: (If applicable)</p> <p>Project website: (If applicable)</p> <p>Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.</p>	<p>PROSPECT+</p> <p>Horizon 2020</p> <p>https://www.h2020prospect.eu</p>
	<p>195 local and regional authorities, matched in 45 groups, exchanged knowledge and experience on how to set up innovative financing schemes to implement their climate and energy measures.</p> <p>45 LEARNING GROUPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 Private Buildings 15 Public Buildings 4 Transport 18 Public Lighting 3 Cross Sectoral <p>18 INNOVATIVE FINANCING SCHEMES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) Soft Loans, Fiscal, Revolving Fund, Lending to ESCOs, Green Bonds, ELENA, PPP, ASC, PPF, H2020 Citizens Finance, Social Funds, Third Party, Cooperative, Crowdfunding <p>190 PROJECTS 36 BEST PRACTICES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5835 GWh Energy Savings / Production 1025 M€ Investments 503 ktCO₂ Reduction <p>29 Cities</p> <p>+53 MILLION CITIZENS</p>
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p> <p>End date:</p> <p>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</p>	<p>01 September 2021</p> <p>28 February 2025</p>
<p>Key benefits / outcomes:</p> <p>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</p>	<p>The ambition of PROSPECT+ is to ensure that over 200 EU cities in at least 20 EU MS improve their capacities when it comes to implementing projects from SECAPs and similar sustainable plans.</p>
<p>References:</p> <p>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly</p>	

Table 6-4. PowerPoor Energy poverty mitigation toolkit.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	PowerPoor Energy poverty mitigation toolkit.
Keywords:	Energy transition planning
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Energy communities
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Innovative financing
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Bulgaria, Croatia, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Portugal, Spain
Region / Municipality / location:	Sofia, Plovdiv, Vidin, Dobrich, Smolyan, Svilengrad, Beloslav (Bulgaria), Zagreb, Križevci (Croatia), Tallinn (Estonia), Megaptera, Corinth, Kalamata, Xylokastro-Evrostini, Messina, Florina, Chalki, Elassona, Eretria, Thiva, Pylos-Nestor, Souli, Aigialeia, Zitsa, Pella, Livadeia, Tripoli, Acharnes, Nikolaos Skoufas (Greece), Józsefváros (8th district of Budapest), Ferencváros (9th district of Budapest), Terézváros (6th District of Budapest), Nyíregyháza (Capital of Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County), and Bükkszentkereszt (Hungary), Jelgava, Jēkabpils, Dobele (Latvia), Ermesinde, Lisbon, Mertola, Sintra, Oeiras, Torres Vedras, Braga, and Portalegre (Portugal), Tolosaldea Region, Oarsoaldea, Bergara, Hernani, Tierra Estella, Iruñea-Pamplona, Vitoria-Gasteiz, Errenteria, Eibar (Spain)
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	The PowerPoor Energy Poverty Mitigation Toolkit aims at providing an integrated solution to users and supporting them at identifying whether they are energy vulnerable.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]</i>	Methodology: The PowerPoor Energy Poverty Mitigation Toolkit can propose changes (behavioral or low cost energy efficiency interventions energy vulnerable households can take to improve their well being. The tool can propose customised solutions regarding their involvement funding proposing the users' involvement in innovative funding schemes such as crowdfunding or participation in energy cooperatives. Energy Poverty Guidebook for energy planning provides support on the use of the PowerPoor Energy Poverty Mitigation Toolkit and on working on the ground with energy-poor households and policy makers to mitigate energy poverty. Digital platform: The PowerPoor Energy Poverty Mitigation Toolkit consists of three tools: (1) Power Target, (2) Power Act, (3) Power Fund.
Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Empowering Energy Poor Citizens through Joint Energy Initiatives / PowerPoor
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://powerpoor.eu/index.php/

<p>Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.</p>	
<p>Progress status - Start date:</p>	<p>09/2020</p>
<p>End date:</p>	<p>08/2023</p>
<p><i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i></p>	
<p>Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i></p>	<p>PowerPoverty has developed support programmes/schemes for energy poor citizens and encouraged the use of alternative financing schemes (e.g. establishing energy communities / cooperatives, crowd funding). PowerPoverty has facilitated experience and knowledge sharing, as well as the implementation of small-scale energy efficiency interventions and the installation of renewable energy sources, increasing the active participation of citizens.</p>
<p>References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online).</i></p>	<p>(1) Energy Poverty Guidebook for energy planning (ENG): https://powerpoor.eu/sites/default/files/2023-04/D5_2%20Energy%20Poverty%20Guidebook%20for%20Energy%20Planning%20V2_2.pdf</p> <p>(2) PowerPoverty Training material (ENG): https://powerpoor.eu/library/training-material</p> <p>(3) Energy Poverty Mitigation Toolkit (ENG): https://powerpoor.eu/sites/default/files/2022-09/POWERPOOR%20-%20D2.5%20Energy%20Poverty%20Mitigation%20Toolkit%20v1.0.pdf</p>

Table 6-5. COMPOSE PLUS

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	COMPOSE PLUS
Keywords:	Energy transition measures
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Methodology / tool / solution
	Energy transition planning
	Training seminars
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Greece, Slovenia, France, Spain, Portugal, Italy, Croatia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Albania, Cyprus
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Municipalities of Rethymnon (Crete, Greece), Anogeia (Crete, Greece) and 16 more around the 10 participating countries.
Short description:	
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	An integrated methodology & digital platform to support MED public authorities in developing High efficiency fireplaces have been demonstrated in rural areas (Anogeia municipality in Crete), rich in wood residues, in order to increase the use of biomass. A feasibility study has assessed the setting up and operation of a local small chips production unit.
Long description:	
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i> <i>Describe a best practice in the field of Training-capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]</i>	The key project objective was to identify appropriate energy mix for small municipalities. Awareness campaign to foster social acceptance and local investments of Small scale RES was implemented in the municipality of Rethymno, Crete, while a local action plan for the upgrade of energy efficiency of fireplaces in a rural community of Anogeia was also elaborated. In particular the project developed: 1) developed a web tool to dimension and to assess quickly the feasibility for small scale RES (small biomass heater, PV installation <2 kWp, family solar thermal boiler) based on a set of parameters and local conditions 2) road show has been implemented with the contribution of RES experts, planners, developers, scientists team in order to inform-discuss-exchange-debate with local communities to address their fears, hesitance, opposition to RES in rural communities with high potential of RES 3) investment opportunities and appropriate financing models has been defined, explained and supported. The cooperation with the local suppliers and engineers was foreseen.
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	COMPOSE PLUS
Funding Programme:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	INTERREG MED-COMPOSE
Project website:	
<i>(If applicable)</i>	https://compose.interreg-med.eu/
Relevant images:	
<i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	

Progress status - Start date:	3/2021
End date:	09/2022
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	15 Pilot cases planned, 18 implemented, based on COMPOSE common methodology. A methodological approach for designing, planning, implementing and evaluating sustainable energy projects was developed to offer insights on how to implement and access RES and energy efficiency measures, exploiting the local potential and integrating not only technical, but also socio-economic and environmental aspects. It can be useful to the policy makers, development planners and local authorities' technical staff involved in the development and implementation of local/regional energy plans to the transition towards low carbon communities.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly available online.</i>	(1) COMPOSE TOOLBOX: https://reselplan-toolbox.eu/ (2) COMPOSE VIDEOS : https://compose.interreg-med.eu/what-we-achieve/deliverables-database/detail/?tx_elibrary_pi1%5Blivrable%5D=7829&tx_elibrary_pi1%5Baction%5D=show&tx_elibrary_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=Frontend%5Clivable&cHash=b67b41568f492b10c41b1b2fd31f77d4 https://compose.interreg-med.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Sites/Renewable_Energy/Projects/COMPOSE/What_we_achieve/WP5_Capitalisation/5.2.5_Policy_recommendations/5.2.5_PolicyRecommendations.pdf

Table 6-6. Peer Learning at EU level with ENERGeE Watch programme.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	Peer Learning at EU level with ENERGeE Watch programme.
Keywords:	Training seminars
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
Country:	Multiple countries
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	Learning programme organised at the EU-level.
Short description:	
(Up to 150 characters)	The peer-to-peer learning programme was designed for local and regional authorities to exchange knowledge about monitoring, reporting, and verification of sustainable policies and measures.
Long description:	
(Up to 1000 characters)	The ENERGeE Watch Learning Programme was organised in 3 cycles, in-person/online, in the period of 2020-2023, gathering from all over Europe representatives of local and regional authorities, energy and climate agencies, researchers and other interested parties. The mentees were offered guidance during the months of the programme and all developed an Action Plan for their region or municipality. Four modules were developed and delivered by experts from four European energy and climate agencies partnering the project:
Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]	1: Energy data collection (acquisition and treatment) 2: Monitoring, reporting, verification: follow up on implementation of actions 3: Indicators and strategies on adaptation to climate change 4: Data display, dissemination and validation by end users
Project full title / acronym:	
The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	ENERGeE Watch
Funding Programme:	
(If applicable)	EU H2020 Programme
Project website:	
(If applicable)	https://energee-watch.eu/
Relevant images:	
Photos, project logo etc.	

Progress status - Start date:	September 2021
End date:	August 2023
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	<p>Over a period of three years, ENERGee Watch developed a peer-to-peer learning programme that has implemented 4 courses over 3 learning cycles.</p> <p>The programme involved 4 mentors, 70 mentees, 18 observers and 10 project partners across Europe, while the replication events gathered roughly 600 people from around 200 organisations within and beyond the EU.</p> <p>Some key lessons learned:</p> <p>The ENERGee Watch learning programme provided versatile knowledge and tools with a high degree of applicability, transferability and scalability, which were all highly valued by mentees;</p> <p>Courses should be offered in multiple formats (online, hybrid, and in-person) to suit a wide range of mentee budgets and availabilities;</p> <p>Sufficient time should be given for one-on-one feedback between mentees and mentors during and after courses.</p>
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly</i>	<p>Final report:</p> <p>https://energee-watch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/ENERGee-Watch-D1.2-Final-Publishable-Report.pdf</p> <p>https://youtu.be/2NkCyGDHJOE</p> <p>Online courses:</p> <p>https://energee-watch.eu/courses-overview/</p>

Table 6-7. Heat and cooling planning capacity building by Act!onHeat project

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	Heat and cooling planning capacity building by Act!onHeat project
Keywords:	Energy transition planning
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Energy Efficiency in buildings
	Renewable energy
	Energy communities
Country:	Multiple countries
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	Germany, Austria, Spain, United Kindom
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Europe
Short description: <i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	The objectives of Act!onHeat are to further disseminate and take up the concept and methods for strategic Heating & Cooling (H&C) planning and increase its quality.
Long description: <i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	The objectives of Act!onHeat are to further disseminate and take up the concept and methods for strategic H&C planning, increase its quality and to push the development and implementation of identified measures. To reach these goals Act!onHeat will implement the following activities: (i) identify the success factors of strong and efficient existing H&C plans and develop a workflow for strategic H&C planning and project development based on the existing open source tools Hotmaps and THERMOS, (ii) support at least 120 municipalities in strategic H&C planning and the development of at least 30 pre-feasibility studies for related individual projects with a mix of tailored individual and group support activities, (iii) train stakeholders who can actively contribute to decarbonisation in the use of workflows, processes and tools through a dedicated training programme, and (iv) leverage additional impact with a mix of Europe-wide roadshow events, acceleration dialogues, webinars and further promotional activities.
Project full title / acronym:	
<i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	From heating and cooling strategies to action: how public authorities can strategically plan the decarbonisation of the heating and cooling sector and initiate impactful projects.
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://actionheat.eu/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	
Progress status - Start date:	06/2021
End date:	25/2024
<i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	
Key benefits / outcomes:	
<i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Train stakeholders who can actively contribute to decarbonisation in the use of workflows, processes and tools through a dedicated training programme.
References:	
<i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is</i>	

Table 6-8. Comprehensive approach to capacity building and training for energy transition within Climate Action Plan 2024-2029 of local council in Ireland.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	Comprehensive approach to capacity building and training for energy transition within Climate Action Plan 2024-2029 of local council in Ireland.
Keywords:	Training seminars
Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.	Energy transition planning
	Renewable energy
	Energy communities
Country:	Ireland
Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.	
Region / Municipality / location:	Carlow town and County
Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).	
Short description: (Up to 150 characters)	Identifying areas for concentrated climate action, including mitigation, adaptation, and biodiversity measures.
Long description: (Up to 1000 characters) Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]	The plan emphasizes several thematic areas, including Governance & Leadership, Built Environment & Transport, Natural Environment & Green Infrastructure, Communities Resilience & Transition, and Sustainability & Resource Management. The implementation of the plan involves a whole-of-Council approach, with the Climate Action Office leading the execution. The plan emphasizes collaboration and partnership with key stakeholders to support its delivery, ensuring a comprehensive approach to capacity building and training for energy transition.
Project full title / acronym: The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.	Carlow Decarbonising Zone (DZ)
Funding Programme: (If applicable)	National funding
Project website: (If applicable)	https://consult.carlow.ie/en/consultation/carlow-county-council-draft-climate-action-plan-2024-2029
Relevant images: Photos, project logo etc.	https://consult.carlow.ie/en/consultation/carlow-county-council-draft-climate-action-plan-2024-2029
Progress status - Start date:	March 2023
End date:	Ongoing
If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.	
Key benefits / outcomes: Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.	A low carbon and climate-resilient community.
References: Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note: please only provide where it is acceptable to make the information publicly	https://consult.carlow.ie/en/consultation/carlow-county-council-draft-climate-action-plan-2024-2029

Table 6-9. Energy Saving Booklet for Waterford households in Ireland.

BEST PRACTICES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	
TYPE OF BEST PRACTICE:	TRAINING - CAPACITY BUILDING
TITLE:	Energy Saving Booklet for Waterford households in Ireland.
Keywords:	Methodology / tool / solution
<i>Please select from dropdown lists (cells B5-B9), up to 5 representative keywords that best describe the features of the best practice.</i>	Renewable energy
	Energy communities
	Energy Efficiency in buildings
Country:	Ireland
<i>Please select from dropdown list (cell B10), the country where the best practice was implemented. If in more than one countries, select "multiple countries" and describe in cell B11.</i>	
Region / Municipality / location:	
<i>Please provide further details on the territory where the best practice was implemented, as applicable (e.g. Region and/or Municipality and/or location of individual building).</i>	Waterford City and County
Short description:	Waterford City and County Council's Climate Action Team has published an Energy-Saving Booklet, developed in direct response to the ongoing global energy crisis which is adversely impacting households and businesses.
<i>(Up to 150 characters)</i>	
Long description:	By 2030, under the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act, national greenhouse gas emissions must be reduced by 51% compared to 2018 levels. Ireland's energy mix is changing. Renewable energy is becoming more widespread, helping to reduce our national emissions. However, until such time as this reaches a sufficient level, we must all play our part to reduce the levels of fossil fuels we use. In response to the energy-related issues facing Irish households, Waterford City and County Council's Climate Action Team have developed this Energy Saving Booklet. Using a common-sense approach to energy saving, the booklet is intended to act as a baseline from which actions can be taken and built upon. While many may be familiar with the tips within, old habits may prevent us from realizing their benefits. Topics covered in the booklet include energy poverty, energy supplier guidance, household appliance
<i>(Up to 1000 characters)</i>	
<i>Describe a best practice in the field of Training - capacity building [e.g. site visits from territories with less mature energy transition plans to other more mature ones already implementing actions; case studies of successful implementation of such activities; etc.]</i>	

Project full title / acronym: <i>The title of the Best Practice is inserted in cell B4. Please only fill in this field (cell B19) if the Best Practice was implemented as part of a "Project". The "Project" can be an EU project or a local / national initiative, a private initiative etc.</i>	Energy Saving Booklet for Waterford households
Funding Programme: <i>(If applicable)</i>	National funding
Project website: <i>(If applicable)</i>	https://waterfordcouncilnews.com/2022/11/23/energy-saving-booklet-for-waterford-households/
Relevant images: <i>Photos, project logo etc.</i>	https://www.waterfordcouncil.ie/media/environment/Energy%20Booklet%20ENGLISH.pdf
Progress status - Start date:	November 2022
End date: <i>If relevant, please include any further information as regards progress of the case study.</i>	Ongoing
Key benefits / outcomes: <i>Describe key benefits - key outputs from this best practice. Where available and relevant, use users' testimonies.</i>	Reduction of CO ₂ emissions through the mitigation of energy-related emissions and to assist households with the management and reduction of their household energy costs.
References: <i>Provide relevant links or documentation (reports / photos / videos etc.) that relate to the described case study (Note:</i>	https://www.waterfordcouncil.ie/media/environment/Energy%20Booklet%20ENGLISH.pdf

7 Conclusions

The Repository of best practices (D6.5) is concerned not only with case studies/projects that the ePLANET partners or pilot regions have participated in but also with wider applicability. The best practices are collected by ePLANET partners from projects they were involved in and from the ePLANET partners' networks of organisations and contacts within their territories.

Each partner (and especially the three pilot partners RDFC, EAZK, and DDGI) forwarded an appropriate template to Municipalities and other public bodies in their territory that may have implemented an interesting best practice relating to energy transition. FEDARENE forwarded the template to the follower Regions. Four National-level partners (CRES, ICAEN) and network partners (FEDARENE/ICLEI) forwarded the template to potential public authorities/stakeholders at the national/broader level who may have implemented an interesting best practice relating to energy transition.

The catalogues of best practices in each category are presented in Table 7-1, Table 7-2, Table 7-3 and Table 7-4.

Table 7-1 Catalogue of best practices and solutions in Governance

Nº	Best Practices and solutions in Governance
1	Committee with participation of Region and its Municipalities, to coordinate energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings
2	Identification of energy governance actors in Catalonia and Greece.
3	One-stop-shop digital platform to allow better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings.
4	Establishment of EU Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG), as a structure for accelerating private finance to energy efficiency.
5	Coordinated project of biomass implementation in 22 Municipalities in Girona.
6	Adoption of EPC Facilitator role to foster EPC contracts.
7	Guidance and advice by the Girona Provincial Council to local councils wishing to promote local energy communities.
8	Innovative Public-Private-Citizen-Partnership (PPCP) for energy governance at local level.
9	Achieving multi-level governance in energy and climate planning.
10	Establishment of Regional observatories for energy transition at local level.
11	Establishment of Permanent Cluster of national HUBs in the Blue Energy sector.
12	Web platform for public consultation with local community, on Municipal strategy for climate neutrality in Heraklion (Crete).
13	Open call to Municipalities to upgrade their water systems with the installation of telemetry, automation and leak control systems, under the National Operational Program.
14	Evaluation of Cretan Municipalities under the framework of the National and Regional Operational Programmes, so as to undertake energy upgrade projects in public buildings.
15	Involvement of secondary school pupils as "Energy Inspectors", in Municipality of Hersonisos (Crete).
16	Memorandum of Understanding among the Region of Crete and 13 Cretan municipalities, for the energy upgrading of public installations.
17	Multivel governance in the Zlín Region.
18	Community Power for homes and businesses in Ireland.
19	Establishment of the European Community Power coalition.
20	Energy Citizenship and Energy Communities for a Clean Energy Transition.

21	Establishment of Minoan Energy Community in Crete.
22	Governance in the Strategy for Energy Building Renovation in Asturias.
23	Kilkenny County Council Climate Change Adaptation Strategy 2019-2024
24	8 Municipal Plans for Climate Action in the territory of Tâmega and Sousa (Portugal).
25	Municipal Energy Saving Plan for the Municipality of Baião (Portugal).

Table 7-2 Catalogue of technical best practices and solutions

N°	Technical Best Practices and solutions
1	Integrated methodology & digital platform to support public authorities in energy-efficiency planning for public buildings.
2	Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings Roadmaps for coordinated regional & local strategies for improving the energy efficiency of public buildings.
3	Open source Big-Data Platform for collection, processing and exchanging energy data from different sources.
4	One-stop shop digital platform tools to analyse and benchmark energy-efficiency measures for public buildings.
5	De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking.
6	Technical information on implemented case studies using biomass in 22 Municipalities in Girona.
7	Guide to facilitating the implementation of local energy communities in Girona.
8	On-line TOOL for a pre-check of EPC availability.
9	EPC model contracting to implement energy efficiency projects for public buildings.
10	4 key tools for energy transition at local level, through a Public-Private-Citizen-Partnership (PPCP).
11	Knowledge Repository platform to support local and regional energy planning & Guidebook to Carbon Neutrality by 2050.
12	Database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe.
13	Technical tools of Regional Observatories to inform local and regional energy transition policies and monitor their implementation.
14	Heraklion 2030 Climate Neutral & Smart City.
15	Promotion of zero-pollutant vehicles in the Greece and Cyprus cooperation area.
16	Improvement of water networks in 6 Municipalities in Crete.
17	Methodology of project categorization and templates with Technical Specifications, for energy upgrade projects in public buildings in Crete.
18	Common methodology for the preparation of Energy Efficiency Investment Plans in more than 70 public authorities in the MED area.
19	Energy management for institutions established by the Zlín Region and for Municipalities of the Zlín Region
20	Enhancing energy efficiency in public buildings in Central Europe by offering best practices, databases of contractors and appliances, financial expertise and a 3D Energy Management System in OnePlace platform.
21	The conceptual approach to the energy efficiency in large hospital area in the Zlín Region with the support from OP Environment
22	Local Energy Communities: «Centrales Villageoises»: a Local Citizen-owned Energy Communities' Success Story
23	EKIOLA: Prosumer PV Cooperatives in the Basque Country

24	Multiple Impacts Calculation Tool
25	C-IZEBs (Cooperative Intelligent education & electromobility Zero Energy Buildings)
26	Biomass district heating network in Roses.
27	Replacement of lighting with LED technology in the municipality of Aiguaviva.
28	Local Energy Communities
29	Electric car sharing service by Som Mobilitat in the municipality of Sant Joan les Abadesses.
30	Biomass heat network for heating and DHW, in Ribes de Freser (Girona).
31	Zagreb's smart energy solutions for citizens.
32	One of Slovenia's first smart grid systems in a public building.
33	SIE - the energy management software.
34	Solar energy potential of buildings in Spain.
35	Energy community planning tool: Som Comunitat Energètica
36	Generating resilient actions against the heat island effect on urban territory.
37	Energy Efficiency in public lighting in the Municipality of Baião.

Table 7-3 Catalogue of best practices in Financing

N°	Best Practices and solutions in Financing
1	Leading role of the Zlín Region in developing low-carbon districts within the Czech Republic.
2	ESCOLIMBURG2020
3	Rénov'Occitanie: One-Stop-Shops for Energy Renovations and Savings in Occitanie.
4	Scaling up the energy refurbishment of public buildings in small and mid-size local authorities.
5	Sun4All financial support scheme for renewable energy access.
6	Solutions Gateway Finance decision-making support tool.
7	Integrated Sustainable Energy Actions and projects in Crete, funded through ELENA.
8	Helping consumers in Castilla y León face the effects of the energy crisis.
9	Engaging citizens and local entities – the “Porto Energy Hub” one-stop-shop.
10	Achieving carbon neutrality in Waterford Council (Ireland).

Table 7-4 Catalogue of best practices in Training activities

N°	Best Practices in Training Activities
1	openENTRANCE
2	EnergyCities: the European learning community for future-proof cities.
3	PROSPECT+: Capacity building for cities and regions - from learning to action!
4	PowerPoor Energy poverty mitigation toolkit.
5	COMPOSE PLUS
6	Peer Learning at EU level with ENERGee Watch programme.
7	Heat and cooling planning capacity building by Act!onHeat project
8	Comprehensive approach to capacity building and training for energy transition within Climate Action Plan 2024-2029 of local council in Ireland.
9	Energy Saving Booklet for Waterford households in Ireland.

